

Deliverable D2: Report on the development of efficient metrological methods for key NR OTA RF parametric metrics (e.g. TRP, EIRP), for sub-6 GHz MIMO and mm-wave massive MIMO systems, and the quantification of the associated uncertainties (target the upper limits of measurement uncertainties for the measured quantities given in 3GPP documents e.g. ETSI TR 38.810, TR 38.884) based on using, for example, direct far-field (DFF), indirect far-field (IFF), near field-to-far-field (NF-FF), mid field and reverberation chamber (RC) methods with validation in an interlaboratory comparison

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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Abbreviations

Acronym	Description
AC	Anechoic Chamber
AiP	Antenna-in-Package
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
AnUT	Antenna under Test
AUT	Array under Test
BS	Base Station
BTM	Backward Transformation Method
BW	BandWidth
CATR	Compact Antenna Test Range
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
CFR	Channel Frequency Response
CTIA	Cellular Telecommunication and Internet Association
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transform
DFF	Direct-Far-Field
DL	downlink
DUT	Device under Test
EIRP	Effective Isotropic Radiated Power
EIS	Effective Isotropic Sensitivity
FSPL	Free-Space Path Loss
HPBW	Half Power Beamwidth
IFFT	Inverse Fast Fourier Transform
IFBW	Intermediate Frequency Bandwidth
LoS	Line of Sight
LTE	Long Term Evolution
MIMO	Multiple-input-multiple-output
mmWave	Millimeter Wave frequency band
MPM	Matrix Pencil Method
MU	Measurement Uncertainty
NAC	Non-Anechoic Chamber
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
Omni-VAA	Omnidirectional Antenna-Based VAA
OTA	Over the Air
PADP	Power Angle Delay Profile
PL	Path Loss
PWG	Plane Wave Generator
QZ	Quiet Zone
RC	Reverberation Chamber
RBW	Resolution Bandwidth
REV	Rotating Element Electric Field Vector method
RF	Radio Frequency
RMSD	Root-Mean-Square Deviation
Rx	Receiver

Acronym	Description
SA	Spectrum Analyzer
SIC	Successive Interference Cancellation
SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
SGH	Standard Gain Horn
Sub-THz	Sub-Terahertz band
SS	System Simulator
THz-TDS	THz Time-Domain Spectrometer
Tx	Transmitter
UE	User Equipment
ULA	Uniform Linear Array
UL	uplink
URA	Uniform Rectangular Array
VNA	Vector Network Analyzer
VST	Vector Signal Transceiver
WP	Work Package
3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project
4G	4th Generation Wireless Systems
5G	5th Generation Wireless Systems
6G	6th Generation Wireless Systems

Contents

Abbreviations	1
Executive summary	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Multi-probe Enabled Over-the-air Calibration of Millimeter-wave Antenna Array: Concept and Experimental Validation	7
2.1 Introduction	7
2.2 Multi-probe enabled array calibration	8
2.3 Multi-probe scheme for improving measurement efficiency	9
2.4 Multi-probe scheme for improving measurement accuracy	11
2.5 Multi-probe scheme for reducing measurement distance	13
2.6 Conclusion	14
3. Over-the-Air Testing for Connecting Faults Diagnosis in Beamforming Antenna Arrays with Short Measurement Distance	16
3.1 Introduction	16
3.2 Proposed beam-steering diagnosis method	17
3.3 Numerical simulations	20
3.4 Measurement validation	20
3.5 Conclusion	22
4 Gradient-Based Beam Peak Search for Over-the-Air Testing of Mmwave Phased Arrays	23
4.1 Introduction	23
4.2 Measurement setup. Search methods used in the standardization and proposed in the current work	23
4.3 Simulation results	26
4.4 Measurement results	27
4.5 Conclusion	29
5 Single-Frequency Phaseless Data Based Echo Suppression for Antenna Pattern Measurement in a Non-ideal Chamber	30
5.1 Introduction	30
5.2 Proposed amplitude-only echo suppression method	30
5.3 Numerical analysis: reliable region, reference antenna selection, zero-frequency pollution, required length of probe movement, number of probe positions (probe spacing) and robustness	35
5.4 Experimental validation	37
5.5 Conclusion	41
6. An Efficient Multi-Beam Pattern Measurement Campaign for Millimeter-Wave Phased Arrays	43
6.1 Introduction	43
6.2 Measurement setup and procedure	43
6.3 Measurement results	45
6.4 Conclusion	50
7. AC Direct Far-field (FF) Measurements of Total Radiated Power (TRP)	51

7.1 Scope	51
7.2 Introduction	51
7.3 3GPP's definition of Total Radiated Power with Anechoic Chamber Method	51
7.4 Far-Field DL Testbed Implementation inside AC	53
7.5 Measurement Procedure of Receiver Path Loss	54
7.6 TRP Test Procedure	56
7.7 TRP Measurement Results	56
7.8 Conclusion	57
8. TRP measurements in RC for 5G FR2 Base Stations	58
8.1 TRP measurements in RISE RC	58
8.2 TRP measurements in NPL RC	65
9. Investigation of high-gain antenna effects during testing in RC at 77 GHz	75
9.1 Scope	75
9.2 Measurement setup	75
9.3 Evaluation of measurement data	75
9.4 Conclusions	78
10. Inter-laboratory Comparisons	79
10.1 Scope	79
10.2 Introduction	79
10.3 Measurement setups for total radiated power using reverberation chamber in RISE and NPL	79
10.4 Measurement results	80
10.5 Conclusion	88
11. Conclusion	89

Executive summary

This report is the third deliverable D2 of the MEWS project, covering the topics included in Work Package 2 (WP2) and it merges the knowledge of the direct far-field (DFF), indirect far-field (IFF), near-field-to-far-field (NF-FF), mid-field and reverberation chamber (RC) methods aiming to develop cost-effective and time-efficient metrological methods for the OTA conformance testing of new radio (NR) RF parametrics.

The chapters of this deliverable report are organized as follows: Chapter 1 gives an overall introduction, while Chapter 2 presents the concepts and experimental validation of multi-probe enabled over-the-air (OTA) calibration of millimeter-wave (mm-wave) antenna array. Chapter 3 describes a novel diagnosis method for connecting faults' detection in beamforming antenna arrays with short measurement distance. Chapter 4 shows an efficient gradient-based beam peak search technique for OTA testing of mm-wave phased array. Chapter 5 proposes a novel echo suppression method with a single-frequency phase-less measurement for recovering the antenna gain pattern measured in the non-anechoic chamber (NAC). Chapter 6 describes an effective multi-beam pattern measurement campaign using a fast multi-beam pattern measuring technique for mm-wave phased array antenna systems characterizations. Chapter 7 presents the total radiated power (TRP) measurements using the direct far field (DFF) method based on the actual 5G NR downlink signal in the anechoic chamber (AC). Chapter 8 presents TRP measurements using the reverberation chamber (RC) method based on the actual 5G NR downlink signal. Chapter 9 shows the investigation of high-gain antenna effects towards OTA conformance testing using RC method at 77 GHz. Chapter 10 shows the inter-laboratory comparisons on the TRP-related measurements between different methods. Finally, conclusions are made in Chapter 11.

1. Introduction

The global shift from 4G to 5G, and soon towards 6G, represents more than just an increase in data rates, it signifies a transformation in how wireless networks are conceived, deployed, and used. Future systems will operate across vastly higher frequency ranges (mmWave and sub-THz), leverage massive antenna arrays, rely on artificial intelligence and edge computing, and serve mission-critical applications requiring extreme precision in timing and reliability [1], [2]. This technological leap introduces unprecedented complexity in the design, testing, and validation of wireless systems. Measurement science or metrology is essential to navigate these challenges, offering the traceable benchmarks necessary for innovation, standardization, regulation, and industrial deployment. However, existing metrology infrastructure and methodologies are not fully equipped to handle these emerging demands.

The primary aim of the presented work in this document is to develop metrological methods that are not only scientifically rigorous, but also practical from an industrial and regulatory standpoint, i. e. minimizing cost and test time while maintaining measurement accuracy and repeatability. A key focus was placed on achieving traceability and uncertainty quantification in accordance with international standards and guidelines. The developed methods aligned with and extended relevant specifications such as [3], [4] and [5].

These metrological advancements support both Radio Frequency (RF) conformance testing (e.g., Total Radiation power (TRP), Effective Isotropic Radiated Power (EIRP)/Effective Isotropic Sensitivity (EIS) validation, spurious emissions, and receiver sensitivity) and end-to-end system performance assessments, including throughput, beam management, and mobility handling under realistic signal conditions. Where relevant, measurement procedures were validated through inter-laboratory comparisons and collaborative test campaigns to demonstrate repeatability and reproducibility across facilities.

More specifically, the main objectives of the deliverable can be summarized as follows:

- Multi-probe Enabled Over-the-air Calibration of Millimeter-wave Antenna Array: Concept and Experimental Validation
- Gradient-Based Beam Peak Search for Over-the-Air Testing of Mmwave Phased Arrays
- Over-the-Air Testing for Connecting Faults Diagnosis in Beamforming Antenna Arrays with Short Measurement Distance
- Single-Frequency Phaseless Data Based Echo Suppression for Antenna Pattern Measurement in a Non-ideal Chamber
- An Efficient Multi-Beam Pattern Measurement Campaign for Millimeter-Wave Phased Arrays

2. Multi-probe Enabled Over-the-air Calibration of Millimeter-wave Antenna Array: Concept and Experimental Validation

2.1 Introduction

Because mmWave technology has a larger spectrum resource than legacy bands (i.e. sub-6 GHz), it is crucial for achieving the high data-rate requirements of current 5G and future wireless communication systems. In dynamic propagation conditions, high-gain and beam-steerable array systems are necessary to maintain link reliability and produce a high Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR), because of the high transmission loss and blockage susceptibility in mmWave bands. Furthermore, because of cost considerations, technological trends in creating highly integrated radio transceiver designs will be unavoidable in mmWave bands [6], [7]. Because of its more stringent requirements for system complexity, implementation cost, and measurement time, this has presented significant hurdles for its testing and measuring methodologies. Therefore, practical, rapid, precise, and affordable methods for evaluating integrated mmWave antenna arrays are urgently required [8], [9], [10] and [11]. To provide precise array radiation performance, rigorous array calibration is necessary. Finding the first complex excitations in the RF chains that are attached to the array elements and calibrating them out to guarantee homogeneous excitation across RF chains is the aim of calibration. Because mmWave radios use active components in the RF channels, array calibration is more important than in legacy frequency bands. For any multi-antenna/channel system to function as intended, array calibration is typically necessary. Research on array calibration has been ongoing for a long time, and numerous techniques have been documented. By taking off the antennas and using an RF cable to reach each antenna port, it is possible to undertake a direct measurement of the RF chain complex responses of individual branches, as demonstrated in [12]. The conducted method's low cost and ease of use have led to its widespread adoption in the industry for legacy frequency bands. However, antenna connectors for testing purposes will not be available due to the highly integrated RF transceiver designs at mmWave and above. Furthermore, because of the higher density packaging made possible by the shorter wavelengths, the number of elements in mmWave phased arrays has increased significantly, making conducted testing impractical. Phased arrays must therefore be calibrated in a radiated Over the Air (OTA) way, particularly for mmWave radios. Antenna elements of the array under test (AUT) are used as interfaces to send and receive plane waves in the boresight direction during OTA array calibration. As a result, the responses in the RF chains and boresight radiation patterns of AUT elements make up the calibration coefficients. There have been reports of mmWave antennas using digital, analog, and hybrid beamforming designs [13] and [7].

The work [14], presented in this subchapter, is focused on calibration for analog-beamforming type phased arrays with amplitude and phase-toggling ability for each element. The park-and-probe technique is commonly used in the industry to simulate plane-wave impinging at each AUT element. It involves moving the probe antenna mounted on a mechanical scanner to line up with each activated AUT element while deactivating other AUT elements (by using of attenuators) and sequentially recording the complex responses for each RF chain [15], [16]. It was shown that mechanical movement is quite slow and inaccurate, especially for large-scale arrays, and thus measurement in this "on-off mode" is not desirable for mmWave phased arrays [17]. By taking into account non-negligible mutual coupling effects between components, the "all-on mode" is able to quantify component-to-component non-uniformity, unlike the "on-off mode". For the mmWave phased array [17], calibration carried out in the "all-on" mode is therefore more accurate. The DFF, Compact Antenna Test Range (CATR), or Plane Wave Generator (PWG) setups can be used to approximate the plane-wave condition in which the AUT can be calibrated in the "all-on mode" [18]. The DFF configuration

necessitates a long measuring distance, may frequently has link budget problems, and has high chamber needs. However, the expense of implementing the system is still significant even though CATR configurations can be used to create plane-wave fields at a distance shorter than the DFF. There have been numerous PWG prototypes suggested for base station (BS) testing in the sub-6 GHz bands [19], [20], and [21]. Although several works have been documented in the literature [22], [23], the applicability of PWGs in the mmWave frequency band is still in its early development, mostly because of the low-resolution of phase shifters and attenuators and the restricted supported bandwidth (BW).

2.2 Multi-probe enabled array calibration

Detailed discussion on the boresight plane-wave methods can be found in [14]. Figure 1 shows the schematic of a multi-probe configuration using M probe antennas.

Figure 1: Calibration system diagram of a multi-probe setup

The multi-probe method is examined in two application scenarios:

1) A multi-probe FF setup to increase the measurement accuracy or measurement efficiency for beam-steering AUT. Plane waves are expected to impinge from probe directions to the AUT.

2) A multi-probe NF setup to shorten the necessary measurement distance. The probes are situated in the FF region of the AUT element, but they are located in the NF region of the AUT. Note that in certain works, this region is referred to as "mid-field" [8], [24].

A single probe antenna can be moved to predetermined positions (a concept known as a virtual probe array) or numerous probe antennas can be used directly to implement the multi-probe system. Note that multi-PWG [25], [26], or multi-reflector compact range (to generate plane waves of varied impinging angles) can also be viewed as a multi-probe technique in a FF configuration. To keep things simple, we'll assume that the probe antennas are turned on and off in sequence.

The idea behind the multi-probe FF setup is that the beam-steering factors of the array can be derived from the array factors associated with the multi-probe locations. This allows for the effective expansion of the beam-steering angular range with sparsely distributed probes [27] and also speeds up the calibration process, because there are fewer

phase settings in the feeding network [28]. In this work, the calibration of the Uniform Linear Array (ULA)-type AUT is the main topic of discussion about the multi-probe FF setup. The probes are arranged in a circle with a radius of R and a center that coincides with the AUT center in the multi-probe FF arrangement. The AUT center is at the boresight direction of each probe antenna, and the multi-probe antennas are pointed toward it.

2.3 Multi-probe scheme for improving measurement efficiency

Detailed information about the basic principles behind the multi-probe FF and NF setups and a discussion can be found in [14]. The reader can refer to Equations (4) - (7) and Fig. 3 - Fig. 5 in [14]. In the current subchapter, several measurement campaigns, which were performed in the Anechoic Chamber (AC), will be presented in order to validate the multi-probe concept for the following objectives:

- 1) Multi-probe scheme for improving measurement efficiency
- 2) Multi-probe scheme for improving measurement accuracy
- 3) Multi-probe scheme for reducing measurement distance

As discussed beforehand, the multi-probe framework can be employed to improve the measurement efficiency compared to the single-probe framework, while maintaining calibration accuracy (guaranteed by the low condition number of the constructed virtual weighting matrix with a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) structure). To experimentally validate it, a multi-probe FF measurement setup implemented by a multi-feed CATR setup with offset-focus multiple feeds was utilized. The employed CATR system consists of nine feeds, which can generate plane waves with nine incident angles (with a 3° interval) at the Quiet Zone (QZ). In our measurement, two plane waves (i.e. mimicking two FF probes on the Receiver (Rx) side), with incident angles of 0° and 6° were generated by the multi-feed CATR setup. A QZ size of 36 cm (width) \times 36 cm (height) can be supported with the CATR. A ULA composed of eight open-ended waveguide antennas with an element spacing of 28.76 mm and operating at 24.95 GHz was employed as the AUT. Note that only the odd AUT elements (i.e. 4 in total) were connected to 2-bit digital phase shifters with a phase adjustment range of 360° and programmable attenuators. Photo of the measurement setup is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Photos of the multi-feed CATR calibration setup

More information about the multi-feed design is available in [29], in which the two feeds (highlighted by the dashed lines in Figure 2) were used in the measurement after calibration.

- Reference “probe and park” on-off measurement

The probe antenna was successively attached to each of the AUT element (“face-to-face” and aligned). Then, only the attached AUT element (one at a time) was activated via setting 0 dB and 0° . All of the other elements were deactivated via setting 60 dB attenuation in the respective links. The measured calibration coefficients were used as the reference.

- Hadamard matrix based measurement

A single Rx feed (mimicking a FF probe in direction 0°) is activated and the phase setting matrix is designed according to the Hadamard matrix [30]. Therefore, four measurement data are recorded, which corresponds to four sets of phase shifter settings in the Hadamard matrix.

- Multi-probe algorithm implemented with two-feed CATR system

The two-probe measurement setup is realized by the use of two Rx feeds. Two sets of phase shifter settings (the way they are defined in (2) in [14] are successively implemented at the AUT element ports. For each set of phase shifter setting, the complex signals are recorded by the individual Rx antennas. Thus, two measurement data (one received at each Rx feed) for each set of phase shifter setting are recorded. A high calibration precision can be obtained in general for both measurements, with an amplitude error of ± 0.7 dB and a phase error of $\pm 4^\circ$ compared to the reference measurement. The errors are mainly due by the phase shifter uncertainties. Based on the obtained validation results, one can conclude that high accuracy can be obtained. The proposed multi-probe method can reduce by two the number of required measurements (i.e. phase shifter settings), when compared to the single-probe method.

The quantity to measure after the array calibration is the whole array radiation pattern. The accuracy of the

calibration and thus the measurement uncertainty (MU) of the final array radiation pattern is dependent on many influences. The antenna pattern is basically a relative field strength or power radiated by an antenna as a function of direction measured in gain (dBi) or radiated power (dBm) as a function of θ, ϕ . The linkage to SI units is here through the field strength measured in V/m or through the power density expressed in W/m². In the reference “probe and park” on-off measurement, the radiation pattern of each element of the Device under test (DUT) antenna and the pattern of the probe antennas must be known. The MU is influenced mainly by the antenna (field probe) calibration and thus the error in measured E -field, the antenna positioning (errors in angular resolution or mounting), polarization mismatch (reduced signal due to misalignment), standing wave distortion of pattern due to chamber reflections and interpolation error due to limited sampling resolution. The MU of the radiation pattern main lobe amplitude measured using a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) is typically ± 0.05 dB and the MU of side lobes can vary from ± 0.2 dB to ± 0.6 dB depending on the lobe amplitude and frequency. The noise in the measured receiving signals and the quantization errors of the phase shifters (settings according to the Hadamard matrix [30] will cause some calibration errors). Simulation of typical amplitude and phase errors of the array is given in [29].

2.4 Multi-probe scheme for improving measurement accuracy

The multi-probe framework can be used to improve the measurement accuracy for phase arrays with limited beam-steering angular range, by virtually broadening the beam-steering range. The measurement setup is explained in details in [27] and only a short description is presented here. The validation measurements were performed in a standard CATR setup, where a 4×4 mmWave phased array was used as the AUT (placed in the QZ of the CATR), as presented in Figure 3. The calibration coefficients of the 1×4 ULA elements can be estimated based on horizontal beam-steering measurements, with each ULA element being a sub-array composed of 4×1 antenna elements. For practical validation of the efficiency of the multi-probe calibration method, two measurements were conducted. The first one uses the rotating element electric field vector (REV) method to obtain the ground truth coefficients of the antenna-in-package (AiP) elements and the second one is the proposed multi-probe calibration method. The AUT was horizontally rotated around the azimuth axis from 90° to -90° with a step of -10° , which is equivalent to multiple probes located in corresponding directions as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: A photo of the measurement setup seen inside the CATR chamber [27]. Note that the control computer and the VNA are outside the chamber and therefore are not shown

For each orientation of the AiP, i.e. each probe location, the AiP performed horizontal beam-steering operations

from -79.2° to 79.2° (total of 65 beam-steering angles). The probe antennas must be placed properly in the multi-probe setup to balance the reduction of the condition number and to achieve good approximation of the AUT element radiation pattern. Although a large probe angular aperture may help in decreasing the condition number, it may lead to large element pattern approximation inaccuracies. A three-probe configuration with two side probes located at $\pm 30^\circ$ is used here. The root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) (defined in [27]) is introduced as a figure of merit to evaluate the calibration accuracy. The RMSD results achieved for this particular setup of 3 probes (positioned at -30° , 0° and 30° of the AUT) are compared with those achieved with the single-probe setup (with the probe located at 0°), when the AUT steer beams within various angular ranges, as illustrated in Figure 27.

Figure 4: Comparison of the calibration results with the DFT matrix-based method for various settings, with the REV method as the reference [31]

It is easy to observe that the precision of the array calibration is significantly affected by the beam-steering angle range. A small angle-steering range leads to a large condition number of the weighting matrix and therefore larger error. However, in the case of a small angle-steering range, the error for the proposed 3-probe setup (illustrated by the red crossed line) is smaller than those for 1-probe setup (blue dotted line). In general, the 3-probe setup provide smaller error compared to the inaccuracy when using the single-probe setup. The measurement results confirm the performance improvement with the proposed multi-probe method. The MU of the calibration is again influenced by imperfectly known radiation patterns of particular array elements and by hardware imperfections of the setup. In particular, the phase shift operation in the phase shifters introduces uncertainties in amplitude and phase (should be measured or taken from the manufacturer datasheet, typically an amplitude uncertainty of ± 0.5 dB and a phase uncertainty of $\pm 5^\circ$ might be expected for each phase state of an 8-bit phase shifter) and quantization errors due to limited phase shift step size $\Delta = (2\pi/2^K)$, where K is the number of bits. Another uncertainty contributions are noise and nonidealities introduced by active components in the phased array (e.g., power amplifiers).

2.5 Multi-probe scheme for reducing measurement distance

The measurement range can be reduced by adopting the proposed multi-probe framework, as it was discussed beforehand. In previous study in [32], the multi-probe concept was validated for a ULA composed of 14 elements. In the current work, the concept will be validated for a 2D rectangular array in an AC (with an even smaller measurement distance than in the cited investigation) in Beihang University, China.

Figure 5: A photo of the measurement setup of the multi-probe NF scheme

A photo of the measurement setup is shown in Figure 5, where a 14×9 non-uniform planar array (with a dimension of $1.124 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m}$) was used as the AUT, operating at frequency of 2.6 GHz. The FF distance of the AUT can thereby be calculated according to the Fraunhofer distance $D_{ff} = 2D^2/\lambda = 2(1.124^2 + 1^2)/0.1154 = 39.2\text{m}$. It is not practical to realize this distance in most ACs. The AUT elements are single-polarized open ended waveguide antennas. Three 32-channel amplitude and phase control network units, each of which consists of a power splitting network, 8-digit programmable phase shifters and a 9-digit attenuators, were connected to the AUT elements. The probe antenna is a standard waveguide WR284 with a typical gain of 5.6 dBi at 2.6 GHz and Half Power Beamwidth (HPBW) of approximately 71° in the H plane and 127° in the E plane, respectively. The probe antenna was attached on a 2D planar scanner, which supports scanning area of 2 m (in the y axis) \times 3 m (in the x axis) with a step of 0.1 mm. The probe antenna moves to form a 10×10 virtual uniform rectangular array (URA) with the same aperture as the AUT in the measurement. Two measurement distances (i.e., 0.5 m and 0.2 m) were used for the multi-probe validation measurements. For simplicity, the transfer matrix between the AUT antenna elements and the probe antennas was recorded by using the on-off mode with the VNA. The on-off measurement for a measurement distance at 0.5 m was conducted and selected as the reference measurement to validate the multi-probe concept. The calibration results with the 10×10 -probe setup at 0.5 m and 0.2 m are presented respectively by blue dots and red crosses in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Calibration results of the 10×10-probe setup with the measurement distance set respectively to 0.5 m and 0.2 m

Good accuracy can be achieved for both of the measurements at distance of 0.5 m (with amplitude errors up to ± 0.3 dB and phase errors up to $\pm 3^\circ$, respectively), and 0.2 m (with amplitude errors up to ± 1 dB and phase errors up to $\pm 6^\circ$, respectively). Compared to the required FF distance of 39.2 m for a single-probe antenna setup, the proposed multi-probe framework can significantly reduce the measurement distance, while in the same time providing a good accuracy. The precision of the calibration achieved at distance of 0.2 m was worse than that for a distance of 0.5 m and it is due to three reasons. The first reason is that a given probe array configuration at a shorter distance covers a larger angular space of each AUT element, which results in a larger interpolation errors. The second one is that the complex signal measurements are less reliable due to high attenuation introduced by AUT element pattern effects, especially for the elements at the edge of the AUT. Of course, the third reason is the more severe coupling presents between the probe antenna and the AUT for the shorter distance case. The MU is similarly to previous cases given mainly by the errors of determination of the probe antenna radiation pattern (see the probe antennas used in [32]), the VNA measurement errors typically ± 0.05 dB (transmission coefficient 0 dB) to ± 0.6 dB (transmission coefficient -70 dB), linearity of the low-noise amplifier and positioning errors. The amplitude uncertainty due to phase shifter quantization is approx. ± 0.5 dB and a phase uncertainty is approx. $\pm 5^\circ$ (8-b programmable phase shifters in [32]).

2.6 Conclusion

Phased array calibration is important to make sure that their radiation performance aligns with the standard requirements prior to a widespread deployment. This subchapter proposes a multi-probe framework to solve the challenges associated with phased array calibration. Three multi-probe schemes are presented and discussed for different objectives, i.e., speeding up calibration measurement, improving calibration accuracy and reducing measurement distance. The basic principle and probe configuration are explained in details for each scheme. Moreover, the advantages and the disadvantages were outlined. Additionally, extensive measurements were performed in ACs for calibrating different AUTs. For the efficiency improvement measurement, it was shown that the number of the required measurements with a two-probe setup can be reduced by two compared to the single-probe setup, with amplitude errors of up to ± 0.7

dB and phase errors of up to $\pm 0.4^\circ$, respectively. For the accuracy enhancement measurement, the three-probe setup can significantly reduce the calibration error, compared to a single-probe setup, especially when the beam-steering angle range is small. For the measurement range reduction measurement, one demonstrated that the distance can be decreased from the required 39.2 m for the single probe setup to 0.5 m with the use of a 10×10 virtual probe array setup, which can achieve amplitude errors up to ± 0.3 dB and phase errors up to $\pm 3^\circ$, respectively. The comparison of various calibration methods in both single-probe and multi-probe setups is summarized in Table I in [14]). The multi-probe scheme is promising for testing future advanced mmWave radios.

3. Over-the-Air Testing for Connecting Faults Diagnosis in Beamforming Antenna Arrays with Short Measurement Distance

3.1 Introduction

Communication systems use beamforming technology to increase the SNR [33]. In order to facilitate multiband operation, BSs in Long Term Evolution (LTE) systems may include up to five arrays, each of which may include eight to eleven dual-polarized antenna elements. The high number of antennas utilized in the BSs causes connecting faults, and this problem gets worse as the number of elements in the sub-6 GHz 5G BS systems increases [34]. The connecting faults include disconnection faults, which may be caused by the deterioration of associated RF components, such as antennas, cables, and connectors. Wrong manual installation can also lead to connecting faults (misconnection faults). Three forms of connecting faults can occur in dual-polarized BS antennas: unconnected antenna elements, switched ports of antenna elements (for the same polarization), and swapped ports of two polarizations of the same antenna element. In traditional array diagnosis methods, the first fault type is the same as the detection of failed elements [35], [36], [31], [37], and [38]. Since the misconnection could negatively impact the beamforming antenna's steering precision, detecting the other two fault types is equally crucial.

In fact, identifying connecting faults with assembled BS antennas in real-world production line environment can be extremely difficult for a number of reasons:

1) The inner antenna structures and feed ports of the assembled beamforming antenna are not visible, since the antenna is enclosed in a radome. Therefore, OTA testing is necessary to assess the device's performance in a non-intrusive manner [39], [40].

2) For assembled antennas, it is not feasible to freely control the phase or amplitude of individual array elements. Beamforming networks that can produce specific specified beam directions [41], [42] are used to create BS antennas with switched beams and electric downtilt capability.

3) To facilitate extensive BS testing, which requires detection based on a small number of measurement positions, the testing method must be quick.

4) It is preferable to use a robust approach that can withstand potential errors from nonideal testing conditions [43]. Without the need for an RF clean environment, i. e. an AC with virtually no environmental scatterings, it would save a significant amount of money. However, overcoming the aforementioned obstacles is not simple.

Few works for achieving array diagnosis will be outlined. A possible method is the backward transformation method (BTM) [35]. It uses planar NF data to reconstruct the FF patterns of the array and the aperture field based on field transformation theory. However, to satisfy the Nyquist sampling theorem, large number of samples and scanners with high precision are required. The REV method [36], [31] is another reconstruction approach. It relies on analysis of the power variation in the array signal while the phase of antenna elements rotates from 0° to 360° . The matrix methods [37], [38], compressed sensing techniques [44], [45] and artificial neural network (ANN)-based techniques ([46], [47] and [48]) have also been proposed as possible methods. However, each of the proposed method has its own limitation or condition in order to achieve a successful diagnosis.

This subchapter is based on [49] and proposes a novel OTA testing method, which can be conducted in a compact measurement setup when a BS antenna operates in its default beam-steering mode. The detection of faulty elements

for various types of connecting faults is achieved by solving the relevant linear equations and implementing a differential strategy. The comparisons between the proposed method and several representative array diagnosis methods mentioned above are summarized in Table I in [49]. The attractive features of the proposed diagnosis method are listed as follows:

1) Default mode measurement: That is, the measurements can be conducted when the AUT, i.e., the beamforming antenna array, steers its beam to the predefined directions using the built-in phase shift settings.

2) Fast: All the antenna elements are diagnosed simultaneously with only a few measurement positions in the NF of the AUT. The whole diagnosis process could be completed in several minutes with the help of a fully automated measurement process.

3) Robust: The proposed method can be achieved in practical indoor or production line scenarios with possible scattering in the testing environment.

3.2 Proposed beam-steering diagnosis method

The schematic of the diagnosis setup is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: BS diagnostics system schematic

Lets assume a beamforming antenna array including N antenna elements (located on the left side of the figure and enclosed by the black dashed line). The feed of the AUT is split into N branches with N phase shifters (one for each branch) connected to the N antenna elements. The phase shifters are used to mimic the built-in phase shift settings of a BS beamforming array. The total number of phase shifter settings is P , allowing for steering the beam into P different directions. The schematic presents also one of the fault types, in particular, the feeds of the third and fourth array elements are swapped. The probe array is located on the right side of Figure 7 and it is also enclosed by the black dashed line. The proposed diagnosis method requires the estimation of the complex S -parameters between

the AUT feed on the left and the probe feed(s) on the right for M different spatial locations. Practically, this could be achieved by either using a probe array with M probe antennas and a switch or by using a virtual probe array i.e., a single-probe antenna is moved to M different locations with the use of a mechanical positioner. The first scheme is preferable to achieve fast diagnosis, because of the possibility for automation of the measurement process. Therefore, the array with M probe antennas and a switch is the method we work with. The distance between the AUT and the probe array is D . Figure 7 presents only one polarization of the AUT and probe array. The other polarization would follow the same arrangement, parallel to the presented one. To detect any connecting faults in the AUT, the array diagnosis is based on estimation of the S -parameter received by M probes for P different phase shifter settings. The measured S -parameter at a single frequency (estimated as complex S_{21} by the VNA in our measurements) forms a matrix $S \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times P}$ with the (m, p) th entry is the S -parameter between the feed of the AUT and m th probe for the p th phase shifter setting ($m \in [1, M], p \in [1, P]$). Matrix S can be expressed as a matrix product of three matrices:

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{B} \quad (3-1)$$

where matrices $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N}$, $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$, and $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times P}$ characterize three factors of the matrix S .

Matrix $\mathbf{A} = [a_{mn}]$ is the coupling matrix between the AUT element ports and the probe antenna ports. Therefore, the elements of matrix \mathbf{A} are the transmission coefficients between the ports of the n th AUT element and the m th probe antenna. Considering that m th probe is placed in the FF of the n th antenna element, matrix \mathbf{A} can be estimated as [50]:

$$a_{mn} = g_n(\theta_{mn}^A) \cdot g_m(\theta_{nm}^P) \frac{j\lambda e^{-jkr_{mn}}}{4\pi r_{mn}} \quad (3-2)$$

Matrix $\mathbf{B} = [b_{np}]$ is composed of P column vectors of the complex excitation weights applied to the N antenna elements. Its single element contains the complex excitation given to the n th AUT element in the p th phase shifter setting. \mathbf{B} can be possibly represented by:

$$b_{np} = B e^{jk(n - \frac{N+1}{2})\delta \sin \alpha_p} \quad (3-3)$$

where B is the magnitude weight for possible tapering, δ is the distance between the AUT elements, and α_p is the target beam steering angle for the p th phase shifter setting. In the following, $B = 1$, i.e. no tapering is assumed. Matrix \mathbf{C} is the connection matrix between the phase shifters and the AUT elements. Under normal condition, each phase shifter is connected to one antenna port and the \mathbf{C} matrix is an identity matrix. However, if a fault occurs, matrix \mathbf{C} is not an identity matrix more. For example, if the n th port is disconnected, then the corresponding diagonal element c_{nn} will be zero. If some ports are swapped, then the corresponding rows or columns in \mathbf{C} will be swapped. Therefore, the matrix \mathbf{C} which gives the information about accidental disconnections of some antenna ports or port swappings, and the structure of the matrix \mathbf{C} shows which antenna ports are affected. To perform a successful diagnosis of the AUT, knowledge about matrix \mathbf{C} and matrix \mathbf{S} is needed.

A diagnosis matrix \mathbf{Q} , i.e., a matrix indicating the fault of the AUT, therefore must ideally be matrix \mathbf{C} from (3-1):

$$\mathbf{Q}_0 = \mathbf{C} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{B}^{-1} \quad (3-4)$$

The elements of matrix \mathbf{S} can be directly estimated by measuring transmission coefficients between AUT and the probe array. \mathbf{B} is generally known and it is defined by (3-3). However, matrix \mathbf{A} is unknown, and the approximation of matrix \mathbf{A} and the inverse operation for both matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} will introduce errors to the diagnosis. Therefore, the accumulation of errors leads to large error and it is therefore not feasible to obtain matrix \mathbf{C} directly. To solve this problem, $\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{C}$ or $\mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{B}$ can be used instead as the updated diagnosis matrix:

$$\mathbf{Q}_1 = \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{C} = \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{B}^{-1} \quad (3-5)$$

or

$$\mathbf{Q}_2 = \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{S} \quad (3-6)$$

The diagnosis matrix from (3-6) is considered as better than the one in (3-5). Matrix \mathbf{A} is estimated by using some simplifications. Moreover, a differential diagnosis is proposed, because it will be more accurate and robust. The reader can refer to [49] for further details. Then, the final diagnosis matrix can be expressed as:

$$d\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{A}_F^{-1} \cdot (\tilde{\mathbf{S}} - \tilde{\mathbf{S}}^{(\text{ref})}) \approx (\mathbf{C} - \mathbf{I}) \cdot \mathbf{B} \quad (3-7)$$

where \mathbf{A}_F^{-1} is the inverse of the simplified matrix \mathbf{A} considering only Free Space Path Loss (FSPL), $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}^{(\text{ref})}$ is the \mathbf{S} matrix of the “golden array” (reference array) and \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix. $d\mathbf{Q} = [q_{np}]$ of P column vectors represents the estimated connection situation of each array element with different scanning angles. A large value of $|q_{np}|$ indicates a big amplitude deviation of the n th element between the AUT array and the “golden array”, showing a possible connecting fault. More specifically, the connecting faults of the n th element in the AUT can be determined by the magnitude of $|q_{np}|$ by following the cases below:

Case 1 : $|q_{n1}| \approx |q_{n2}| \approx \dots \approx |q_{nP}| \approx 0$. In this case, the n th antenna element works correctly.

Case 2 : $|q_{n1}| \approx |q_{n2}| \approx \dots \approx |q_{nP}| \gg 0$. In this case, there is a disconnection fault or a misconnection of swapped ports for antenna element polarization on the n th antenna element.

Case 3 : $|q_{n1}| < |q_{n2}| < \dots < |q_{nP}|$. In this case, there is a misconnection fault of swapped ports (for the same polarization) on the n th antenna element. Note that $|q_{np}| > 0$ when the p th phase shift setting does not correspond to 0° scanning angle for Case 3.

3.3 Numerical simulations

CST Microwave Studio have been used to obtain the S-parameters of the reference array i.e., matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}^{(\text{ref})}$, and simulations in MATLAB are used to validate the entire diagnosis process. An 11-element beamforming antenna array presented in Figure 8 serves as the AUT in our simulation.

Figure 8: Arrangement of the AUT and the probe array

The antenna element is a $\pm 45^\circ$ polarized antenna and it operates at 2.7 GHz. The array has 22 ports in total, with 11 ports for each polarization. The distance between elements is 72.2 mm (which is equivalent to 0.65λ at 2.7 GHz). The beam can be steered from 0° to 15° with a step of 3° . The array in Figure 8 is used for validation of the proposed diagnosis method. However, the proposed method is not limited to this particular type and arrangement of the array elements. As it is presented in the figure, the fault types are detected by a linear array of probes arranged opposite to the AUT. The probes should be dual-polarized in the same directions as the AUT. The distance between the AUT array and probe array is selected to be 40 cm (around 3.6λ) to obtain small system errors. Matrix \mathbf{A} is a matrix of transmission coefficients between the AUT and probes at 2.7 GHz obtained from the simulations in CST Microwave Studio. The effectiveness of the proposed method is demonstrated in Figure 9 and Figure 11, showing the simulation and the measurement results for different types of connecting faults.

3.4 Measurement validation

A measurement system was built in a laboratory environment at Aalborg University for validation of the proposed method, as presented in Figure 10a, and photos of the measurements are shown in Figure 10b and Figure 10c.

Figure 9: Simulation results: Magnitude of the differential diagnosis matrix $d\mathbf{Q}$ for fault type of a) element 3 disconnected and b) elements 3 and 4 swapped

Figure 10: (a) Illustration of the measurement system, photos of (b) measurement system and (c) configuration of the AUT and probe antennas

For simplicity, the diagnosis for an 8-element single-polarized linear array was demonstrated. The measurement data were recorded at center frequency of the AUT, i. e. 3.6 GHz. The AUT and the probe antennas are aligned, numbered, and set face-to-face as shown in Figure 10c. The distance between the AUT and the probe array was 100 cm (around 12λ). The height of the antennas is 150 cm.

Figure 11: Measurement results: Magnitude of the differential diagnosis matrix $d\mathbf{Q}$ for fault type of a) element 4 disconnected and b) elements 4 and 5 swapped

As it is obvious from Figure 9 and Figure 11, for both simulation and measurement set-ups, the disconnected elements and the swapped elements have been detected successfully (by identifying the peaks in the amplitude values).

As pointed out in [49], the precise magnitude of peaks is not crucial as rather the variation trend determines the type of fault. The hardware used in the experiment [49] is not ideal. For instance the 8-way power divider may introduce amplitude balance up to 0.4 dB and phase error up to 8° , the phase shifter specified accuracy is $\pm 1.5^\circ$. Moreover, the isolation among arms is reported to minimum 20 dB, which means in the worst case each transmission path is influenced by adjacent paths as well. The setup was first calibrated for these imperfections with typical amplitude deviation for different paths within ± 0.15 dB and phase difference $\pm 0.6^\circ$ whereas the MU of the transmission coefficient measured using VNA is typically ± 0.1 dB and $\pm 1^\circ$, respectively, for transmission coefficients up to -70 dB. Compared with the magnitudes of the matrix elements, the type of fault can still be determined unambiguously even with a non-ideal hardware.

3.5 Conclusion

A novel diagnosis method based on the measurement of S -parameters between the AUT and a probe array is presented for connecting faults' detection in beamforming antenna arrays. Generally, the probe array which must be the same as the AUT positioned at short simulation (measurement) distance from the AUT can be used for diagnosis, as the proposed method has been verified both by simulations and measurements. The proposed method functions for a beamforming antenna array working in its default beam-steering mode. The MU introduced by the hardware setup is negligible compared to magnitudes of matrices required to detect a fault in the antenna array.

4 Gradient-Based Beam Peak Search for Over-the-Air Testing of Mmwave Phased Arrays

4.1 Introduction

EIS and EIRP are important metrics that must be precisely measured at the beam peak directions in order to assess the transmit and receive performance of mmWave antennas. It is time-consuming to properly record the entire radiation pattern of the DUT in order to determine the beam peak direction. The problem gets more complicated, because the more directive beam patterns generated by larger-aperture antennas in future mmWave systems require more dense sampling [51]. Thus, a beam peak search approach that is both precise and efficient is urgently needed. The maximum total component of EIRP defines the beam peak direction, including the corresponding polarization of the DUT used to form the beam, as defined in the Cellular Telecommunication and Internet Association (CTIA) and the Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) [52]. 3GPP and CTIA have provided clear instructions on the measuring process [53], [54]. [53] states that the beam peak search procedure in the spherical coverage test uses either a constant step size grid approach or a constant density grid method. In particular, the constant step size technique requires at least 1106 grid points for the reference 8×2 non-sparse antenna arrays used in smartphone UEs, and the constant density grid method requires 800 grid points. This procedure takes a lot of time and is not acceptable in the industry [55]. There is a significant need to limit the number of measurements in order to shorten the measurement time.

This subchapter is based on the work in [56], and proposes a gradient-based search method, which reduces significantly the number of required measurement points compared to conventional search method, while maintaining the measurement accuracy. Moreover, a coarse and a refined strategies are presented to mitigate the problem of gradients potentially converging to local maxima rather than global maxima. Numerical simulations and experimental measurements have been performed to validate the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm.

4.2 Measurement setup. Search methods used in the standardization and proposed in the current work

Measurement system for the beam peak search is presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12: The schematic diagram of measurement system with measurement points (circle)

Positioned on a turntable, the mmWave phased array DUT forms and fixes a beam in a predetermined direction. A probe antenna samples the radiation pattern of the DUT at each point of rotation (by using a constant step or density grid). To guarantee the robustness of the measurement process, the turntable is randomly rotated and the relative orientation of the antenna array and the measurement grid is also changed randomly in accordance with the 3GPP

specification. The antenna array model in [57] is used to construct the radiation pattern. The DUT is an 8×2 rectangle phased array with 0.5λ vertical and horizontal spacings. Each array element has a front-to-back ratio of 30 dB and a horizontal HPBW of 260° and a vertical HPBW of 130° . As shown in Figure 13a, the reference antenna pattern has a beam peak at $[0^\circ, 0^\circ]$.

Figure 13: a) The radiation pattern of reference antenna array with $\theta = 0^\circ$, Diagram for coarse measurement: b) Measured EIRP over the coarse grid c) The interpolated radiation pattern and vertices identified as the potential beam peak location

According to the standardization, the probe antenna moves in the θ and ϕ directions with a step size of 7.5° , while the DUT rotates in a random direction, creating a grid of 1106 measurement points. For the duration of the measurement, the probe antenna is positioned at grid point $[\theta, \phi]$ with the beam fixed toward the DUT. The signal sent by the DUT is then picked up by the probe antenna. A spectrum analyzer (SA), power meter, or gNB simulator is then used to process the received signal in order to precisely measure its power level. Next, EIRP is computed by summing the measured power with the composite losses of the entire transmission path and frequency. The beam peak direction is determined at the angular location where the maximum EIRP is found after the EIRP is measured at all grid points using the previously described steps.

The steps of the proposed method are summarized in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Proposed method

Input: Size of sparse grid $G_r \times G_c$

Output: $\mathbf{x}_{\text{peak}}, \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{mat}} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_R]^\top$

- 1: Measure $G_r \times G_c$ sparse grid matrix $E(\mathbf{x}_{a,b}^{s1})$ and calculate the 181×181 matrix \tilde{E} by interpolation
- 2: Identify potential beam peak location \mathbf{x}_p^{s2} and $\mathbf{x}_{p,q}^{s3}$
- 3: Measure \mathbf{x}_p^{s2} and $E(\mathbf{x}_{p,q}^{s3})$, \mathbf{x}_1 is the location with maximum EIRP among \mathbf{x}^{s1} , \mathbf{x}^{s2} and \mathbf{x}^{s3}

4: $K = 100, k = 1$

5: **while** $k \leq K$ **do**

6: Calculate the search direction ρ_k and step size l_k with the \mathbf{x}_k based on (9)-(13) in [56]

7: Update the measurement position \mathbf{x}_{k+1} based on (8)

8: When $E(\mathbf{x}_{k+1}) \leq E(\mathbf{x}_k)$ is satisfied three times, $\mathbf{x}_{\text{peak}} = \mathbf{x}_k, R = k$, **break**

9: $k = k + 1$.

10: **end while**

Because of its ability to determine quickly the next search direction [58], [59], the gradient search method is computationally efficient when compared to other optimization algorithms like genetic algorithm and particle swarm optimization. Additionally, the gradient search method's converging to local maximum issue can be successfully mitigated by combining a coarse and refined strategy. The equipment, calibration requirements, and measurement systems used in the standard method and the proposed technique are identical. The proposed method starts with a sparse grid and uses a gradient method to adaptively pick measurement points, producing variable measurement grids that rely on the DUT orientation, in contrast to the standard method, which employs a fixed grid. We describe the procedure of the proposed method as follows below, assuming that the DUT is rotated randomly [60].

The optimal initial position \mathbf{x}_1 for refined measurement is determined by a coarse measurement process. The detailed procedure is:

1. Measurements are performed on a sparse grid of $G_r \times G_c$ with $d_\theta = 180/G_r$ and $d_\varphi = 180/G_c$ sampling step sizes in θ and φ directions, respectively. The received power is recorded at the different grid points $\hat{E} \in \mathbb{C}^{G_r \times G_c}$, and the measured EIRP is presented in Figure 13b.
2. The radiation pattern $\tilde{E} \in \mathbb{C}^{181 \times 181}$ with 1° resolution can be interpolated based on the measured data. It is presented in Figure 13c.
- 3) The location of vertices, where the EIRP at these positions are bigger than the EIRP of all surrounding these positions, can be extracted based on the interpolated radiation pattern \tilde{E} . The defined vertices are potential positions for the beam peak points. The locations $\tilde{X}_v \in \mathbb{C}^{2 \times N_v}$ and EIRP $\tilde{E}_v \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times N_v}$ at and around vertices are recorded. N_v is the number of vertices.
- 4) \mathbf{x}_1 is the location of the maximum value in \tilde{E}_v .

Based on the \mathbf{x}_1 obtained in the coarse measurement process, the refined measurement process is performed. The update of the measured position is done in accordance to [61]:

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{x}_k + l_k \rho_k, \quad (4-1)$$

where ρ_k is search direction and l_k is step size, $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$, K is the number of the updates. The search space is $[-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ and $[0^\circ, 180^\circ]$ for θ and φ dimensions respectively. Prior to the procedure start, the restriction of update times $K \leq K_m$ needs to be set. K_m is the maximum number of updates and \hat{L} is the maximum number of loops \hat{L} . Therefore, if the same update result $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{x}_k$ is obtained more than \hat{L} times, the procedure must stop.

Starting from \mathbf{x}_1 , equation (4-1) is repeated in the search space, during each update, the next measurement

point x_{k+1} can be estimated by calculating l_k and ρ_k according to the gradient of the current measurement point x_k . For detailed explanation about all equations used in the proposed method, the reader can refer to Equations (2)-(7) in [56].

4.3 Simulation results

Simulated and measured radiation patterns are used to compare the performance of the standard and proposed methods. MmWave patch antennas are utilized for the experimental investigation, while synthetic patterns are used for the simulations. The mean number of required points is used to calculate measurement time. By statistically analyzing 50,000 random orientations and computing the mean error and standard deviation (STD), accuracy is assessed. The offset that contains 95 % of the peak error distribution is known as the MU of the maximum EIRP. The statistical results from simulation and the 3GPP standardization [53] are presented in Table I.

TABLE I
STATISTICAL RESULTS OF CONSTANT STEP SIZE GRIDS

Step [°]	Number	Mean Error [dB]		STD [dB]		MU [dB]	
		<i>From</i> [8]	Simulation	<i>From</i> [8]	simulation	<i>From</i> [8]	simulation
2.5	10226	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.05
5	2522	0.07	0.08	0.07	0.10	0.21	0.25
7.5	1106	0.16	0.19	0.15	0.25	0.48	0.59
10	614	0.29	0.36	0.27	0.51	0.84	1.11

For a reference, the data from [53] is used. The results confirm the reliability of results, because good alignment with the reference data is obtained. In order to get a MU of 0.5 dB or less, at least 1106 grid points (or a 7.5° step size) are needed for beam peak search in accordance with the standard. However, the standard method requires a fine grid search even in sectors with low EIRP and therefore making it time-consuming and not efficient.

Figure 14: Search process of the proposed method, coarse measurement (\hat{E} is rectangle, \tilde{E}_v is rhombic) and refine measurement (circle): (a) 1 vertex in coarse measurement. (b) multiple vertices in coarse measurement

With a precision of 1°, the simulation range for the azimuth angle ϕ is from 0° to 180° and the elevation angle θ is from -90° to 90°. One issue of the gradient-based approach is that it might be challenging to distinguish between a local peak (on a side lobe) and a global peak (on the main lobe) when the gradient is near zero. Therefore, the

proposed method can be used to lessen this issue. Figure 14a presents the detection of a single vertex, while Figure 14b illustrates multiple detected vertices. The coarse measurement procedure confines the refined search to the main lobe. Figure 14 presents that the beam peak is successfully found with 67 and 89 measurements respectively, achieving 0.09 dB EIRP errors and $[1^\circ, 2^\circ]$ in Figure 15a, and 0.05 dB and $[0^\circ, 1^\circ]$ in Figure 15b.

The proposed method is simulated with a 5×7 coarse measurement grid and chosen parameters $K_m = 100$ and $\hat{L} = 2$ to achieve a balance between the exploration and the exploitation. The histogram and Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) distribution of the statistical results of the standard method and proposed method can be found in Fig. 5 in [56].

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF STATISTICAL RESULTS OF BEAM PEAK SEARCH METHODS FOR REFERENCE DUT

Method	Mean Number	Mean Error [dB]	STD [dB]	MU [dB]
From [8]	1106	0.16	0.15	0.48
Proposed	79	0.22	0.34	0.95

Table II presents statistical results of the standard and the proposed methods. The measurement points are reduced by 92.9 % on average for the proposed method compared to the standard method, while keeping the deviation of each statistical indicator within 0.5 dB. Furthermore, it is proved that without the coarse and refined strategy, the algorithm may detect the beam peak at the side lobes (it converges to the local maximum) rather than at the main lobe. Therefore, the deployment of the coarse and refined strategies may improve significantly the accuracy of the algorithm.

4.4 Measurement results

The proposed algorithm is applied on measured phased array radiation pattern data in order to verify its effectiveness. Each of the three mmWave phased array DUTs has been tested in a typical AC using a direct FF measurement setup at 26.5 GHz, 28 GHz, and 29.5 GHz. With a resolution of 1° , the measuring range is 0° to 180° for φ and -90° to 90° for θ . The results of applying the proposed method to the measured radiation patterns are shown in Table III.

TABLE III
SEARCH RESULTS OF PROPOSED METHOD FOR MEASURED DUT

DUT	Freq. [GHz]	Number	EIRP Error [dB]	Loc. Error [deg]
I	26.5	63	0.32	$[2, 1]$
	28	65	0.12	$[1, 0]$
	29.5	80	0.23	$[10, -1]$
II	26.5	67	0.09	$[1, -3]$
	28	77	0.06	$[-1, 6]$
	29.5	52	0.45	$[3, 3]$
III	26.5	70	0	$[0, 0]$
	28	59	0.06	$[1, 0]$
	29.5	66	0.28	$[-4, -4]$

Figure 15: Searching results on measured DUT: (a) 0 dB EIRP error and $[0^\circ, 0^\circ]$ location error for DUT III at 26.5 GHz. (b) 0.23 dB EIRP error and $[10^\circ, -1^\circ]$ location error for DUT I at 29.5 GHz

The average location error was $[2.6^\circ, 2^\circ]$, the average number of measurement points was 67, and the maximum and average errors were respectively 0.45 dB and 0.18 dB. The success of the proposed approach is demonstrated by the high accuracy in the search results across the three DUTs. The beam peak on the DUT III radiation pattern at 26.5 GHz is precisely identified in Figure 15a. The search procedure for the radiation pattern of DUT I at 29.5 GHz is shown in Figure 15b. The low flatness at $[0^\circ, 5^\circ]$ causes the variation in direction selection in Figure 15b. However, the location mistake is minimal because the found maximum is only 0.2 dB lower than the actual maximum of 26.5 dB, at 26.3° .

When determining the maximum and average errors of the EIRP (or EIS) and location, one has to take into account the MU given by the measurement setup. There are several uncertainty contributions:

- Transmitter power uncertainty. This component is mainly caused by the variability in source power. The power stability of a bench-top signal generator is usually very good at 26.5 GHz to 30 GHz used in this study (within ± 0.05 dB). The situation changes when using a power amplifier which is usually less stable and is sensitive to temperature changes. Despite significant reduction of test time using the proposed method, the test with 60-70 points still takes some time and the amplifier amplitude might change up to $\pm(0.2 - 1)$ dB.
- Antenna gain calibration. This uncertainty component is caused by the errors in gain measurement of the DUT or probe antenna. As indicated above, the amplitude is evaluated using a SA, power meter or a gNB simulator. A SA is usually very well linear and can measure with very small error in high dynamic range up to 100-120 dB provided the absolute level measurement is calibrated against a reference power sensor. The typical level error for a bench-top SA is less than $\pm 0.1-0.2$ dB at frequencies around 30 GHz. If the level is measured using a power sensor, the limited dynamic range may influence the measurement of low levels (a typical dynamic range of broadband power sensors is 40-50 dB and then the MU quickly rises for low levels). The typical MU of a power meter is less than 0.1 dB. In contrast to tuned level measurements in a SA, a power meter measures the power in its whole operating BW, i.e. including possible higher harmonics and non-harmonics caused by the amplifier. Especially for diode-type power sensors the other unwanted spectral components may contribute to the measured power error significantly. The power level accuracy of a gNB simulator is usually much worse compared to a SA of power meter and thus the MU of the EIRP (EIS) would be much higher.
- Path loss (PL) measurement. This MU component is given by errors in the chamber or free-space path calibration

and its size is mainly dependent on the power level measurement accuracy.

- Positioning. The turntable may have a positioning uncertainty which is specified in the manufacturer datasheet. The location error of the maximum gain is then influenced by the angular alignment errors of the turntable.
- Temperature variations. They can affect the DUT performance (especially if the DUT is composed of active components) or chamber and power amplifier characteristics. The magnitude of this MU component is estimated from the datasheet of the DUT or the chamber/amplifier.

4.5 Conclusion

In order to estimate the beam peak for mmWave wireless devices with the fewest possible measurements, this subchapter presents an efficient gradient-based beam peak search technique. The results demonstrate that the proposed method, which uses a gradient-based approach to locate the beam peak in contrast to 3GPP's brute-force search method, significantly reduces the number of required measurements, while preserving accuracy. According to the simulation data, a reduction in the measurement time by 92.9 % and an average inaccuracy of 0.22 dB are obtained for the 8×2 phased array, while an error in the amplitude of 0.18 dB and an improvement in the measurement time of 93.9 % for the mmWave patch antennas in experiments. Furthermore, future research should examine its application for more complex radiation patterns.

5 Single-Frequency Phaseless Data Based Echo Suppression for Antenna Pattern Measurement in a Non-ideal Chamber

5.1 Introduction

In the DFF setup for accurate antenna pattern measurement, there is a need for a large AC, which can provide Line of Sight (LOS) propagation path with a planar wavefront between the probe antenna and the Antenna under Test (AnUT) [62]. However, high-performance absorbers and a large AC are required. Therefore, it can not be met by most research institutions and therefore this method cannot be used for massive AUT testing. Additionally, there are cases in which the multi-path environment can not be avoided due to proximity of the antenna placed to the chamber wall, reflections from objects, which cannot be covered by absorbers, and undesired performance of radio absorbers. Diverse echo suppression techniques have been proposed in [63], [64], [65], [66], [67], [68] and [69]. Unfortunately, all these algorithms typically require many complex-signal measurements.

The content of this chapter is based on the work [52], in which a novel echo suppression method using the single frequency amplitude-only information is presented for the 2-D FF antenna measurement in a NAC. Firstly, a reference antenna is measured at different spatial locations in order to evaluate an environment factor, which is then used to recalculate the actual AnUT pattern. The main contributions can be summarized as:

- 1) Complex signal measurement is not needed, because it requires power only measurement. Therefore, this method simplifies the measurement and reduces the hardware cost.
- 2) The proposed method is a single frequency technique and there is not any requirement on the supported BW of the DUT. The latter can be attractive for commercial radios with a limited supported BW.
- 3) An excellent measurement efficiency, because the proposed algorithm requires only a few measurement locations, which is easy for implementation in an automatic manner.

5.2 Proposed amplitude-only echo suppression method

The measured AUT $A_{AUT}^M(\phi)$ pattern, considering the multipath effects and neglecting the noise, can be written as:

$$A_{AUT}^M(\phi) = \sum_{l=1}^L a_l \exp(j\varphi_l) A_{AUT}(\phi - \phi_l) \quad (5-1)$$

where $A_{AUT}(\phi)$ is the true (real) pattern of the AnUT to be estimated. L is the number of propagation paths, including the LOS path. ϕ denotes the orientation of the AUT, with $\phi = 0^\circ$ depicting the AnUT and probe antenna face-to-face aligned. a_l , ϕ_l , and φ_l are respectively the amplitude, impinging angle, and phase of the l th propagation path, with $a_1 = 1$ and $\phi_1 = 0^\circ$ characterizing the LOS path. The measured AUT $A_{AUT}^M(\phi)$ pattern can be represented as the spatial convolution of the true antenna pattern and the spatial channel response:

$$A_{AUT}^M(\phi) = A_{AUT}(\phi) * B(\phi) \quad (5-2)$$

where $*$ denotes the circular convolution operator and $B(\phi)$ denotes the channel response vector that can be expressed as:

$$B(\phi) = \sum_{l=1}^L a_l \delta(\phi - \phi_l) \exp(j\varphi_l) \quad (5-3)$$

It is obvious that if the channel characteristics vector $B(\phi)$ is known, then the true (real) pattern $A(\phi)$ can be obtained from $A_{AUT}^M(\phi)$ via compensating out the channel vector $B(\phi)$. In [52], it is explained that after performing DFT for (5-2) in the angular domain, the convolution relationship is transformed into the multiplication relationship. Therefore, for the true (real) pattern $A(\phi)$ we obtain:

$$\tilde{A}_{AUT} = \tilde{A}_{AUT}^M / \tilde{B} \quad (5-4)$$

where \sim denotes the DFT operation. The division is implemented element-wise in the DFT vectors. Thus, if \tilde{B} is known, the true (real) pattern can be estimated by performing the IDFT for (5-4), and \tilde{B} can be considered as the calibration factor. Obviously, the key to spatial deconvolution for the true pattern is to obtain the calibration factor \tilde{B} . Generally, there are two main methods to estimate \tilde{B} , i.e. chamber channel sounding method [70] and reference antenna method [71].

In the chamber channel sounding method, the spatial matrix pencil method (MPM) is used with the formed virtual array in the chamber (i.e., by moving a single antenna to several preset spatial locations and measuring the chamber channel response at each spatial location) [70]. Therefore, the environment multi-path characteristics, i.e., the propagation angles, amplitudes, and phases, can be estimated. Then, $B(\phi)$ can be calculated from (5-3), and the calibration factor \tilde{B} is estimated with the use of DFT. This method is used widely for channel parameter estimation in wireless communication [72]. However, the effectiveness of the method depends on the virtual array aperture (i.e., the spatial resolution) and therefore requires a high SNR.

The other method, i.e. the reference antenna method, extracts the calibration factor by using a reference antenna with known pattern $A_{REF}(\phi)$. Therefore, the pattern measurement for the reference antenna in the nonanechoic environment is firstly conducted, resulting in a measured pattern $A_{REF}^M(\phi)$ yielding:

$$A_{REF}^M(\phi) = A_{REF}(\phi) * B(\phi) \quad (5-5)$$

By applying DFT operation to (5-5), the calibration factor can be estimated as:

$$\tilde{B} = \tilde{A}_{REF}^M / \tilde{A}_{REF} \quad (5-6)$$

Without changing the channel environment, the AUT pattern $A_{AUT}^M(\phi)$ can be measured. Then, by substituting (5-6) into (5-4), the true pattern in the DFT domain can be reconstructed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{AUT} &= \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{AUT}^M / \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \\
&= \frac{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{AUT}^M \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{REF}}{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{REF}^M}
\end{aligned} \tag{5-7}$$

Thus, $A_{AUT}(\phi)$ can be easily computed by performing the IDFT.

In the proposed method, the probe antenna is placed in the FF of the AnUT and it is moved along the LOS path direction to M positions spaced by Δd , as illustrated in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Diagram of the FF antenna measurement in a NAC, where the AUT is rotated in a counterclockwise direction, starting from -180° , as denoted by the gray arrow. Note that in this figure the antenna under test is denoted as AUT

In general, the amplitude of the propagation paths over the multiple probe locations is distance-dependent due to the FSPL. However, since the FF measurement setup is considered here and the probe virtual array aperture is much smaller compared to the FF measurement distance d_0 , the variation in the path power among the probe virtual array introduced by the FSPL can be ignored. Neglecting the probe antenna pattern, with the measured antenna rotated to ϕ , the FF received signal can be represented as a vectorial summation of complex signals (complex field of direct path and reflected paths). The reader is advised to refer to equations (9)-(11) in [52].

The received power at the m th probe position for a given AnUT rotation angle ϕ can be represented as the squared magnitude of the complex received signal $y(m, \phi)$. If we considering the non-anechoic environment with an LOS propagation and two reflection paths, then the received power $P(m, \phi)$ at the m th position for a given AUT rotation angle ϕ can be calculated by using (10), where $(\cdot)^H$ is the conjugate operation. Note that $y(m, \phi)$ is the FF received signal, $E_l(\phi)$ is the complex amplitude of the l th propagation path at the original ($m = 0$) position with $E_1(\phi)$ denoting the contribution of the LOS propagation, Φ_l is the received signal phase that is jointly determined by the l th wave propagation and antenna phase pattern response and k_l can be considered as the spatial frequency of the l th propagation wave along the direction of movement. Terms I-III in (5-8) can be considered as the direct components, which are important in the proposed method. Terms IV-VI can be considered as the harmonic components, which are characterized by the spatial frequency differences $(k_i - k_j)$ caused by the i th and j th propagation paths.

$$\begin{aligned}
P(m, \phi) &= y(m, \phi) \cdot y^H(m, \phi) \\
&= |E_1(\phi)|^2 + |E_2(\phi)|^2 + |E_3(\phi)|^2 + E_1(\phi)E_2^H(\phi) \cdot \exp(j2\pi(k_1 - k_2)m\Delta d) + E_1(\phi)E_3^H(\phi) \cdot \exp(j2\pi(k_1 - k_3)m\Delta d) \\
&\quad + E_1^H(\phi)E_2(\phi) \cdot \exp(j2\pi(k_2 - k_1)m\Delta d) + E_1^H(\phi)E_3(\phi) \cdot \exp(j2\pi(k_3 - k_1)m\Delta d) \\
&\quad + E_2(\phi)E_3^H(\phi) \cdot \exp(j2\pi(k_2 - k_3)m\Delta d) + E_2^H(\phi)E_3(\phi) \cdot \exp(j2\pi(k_3 - k_2)m\Delta d) \\
&= \underbrace{|E_1(\phi)|^2}_{\text{I}} + \underbrace{|E_2(\phi)|^2}_{\text{II}} + \underbrace{|E_3(\phi)|^2}_{\text{III}} + \underbrace{2|E_1(\phi)||E_2(\phi)|\cos(2\pi(k_1 - k_2)m\Delta d + \Phi_1(\phi) - \Phi_2(\phi))}_{\text{IV}} \\
&\quad + \underbrace{2|E_1(\phi)||E_3(\phi)|\cos(2\pi(k_1 - k_3)m\Delta d + \Phi_1(\phi) - \Phi_3(\phi))}_{\text{II}} + \underbrace{2|E_2(\phi)||E_3(\phi)|\cos(2\pi(k_2 - k_3)m\Delta d + \Phi_2(\phi) - \Phi_3(\phi))}_{\text{VI}}
\end{aligned} \tag{5-8}$$

Further, the reader can refer to Fig. 2 - Fig. 14 and equations (13)-(20) in [52], which for the sake of simplicity are not included in the deliverable. However, they will be briefly discussed.

The most important part of the proposed method is to extract the direct components in (5-8). Considering as an example a simulated measurement with $M = 32$ positions, the procedure is detailed as follows:

1. Measure the received power at all M positions and obtain the power sequence (shown in Fig. 2(a) in [52]).
2. Perform DFT for the obtained power sequence (the harmonic frequency spectrum is shown in Fig. 2(b) in [52]).
3. The direct components must appear at zero frequency. The harmonic spectrum value at zero-frequency point must be directly extracted. More specifically, by nulling the harmonic frequency components except that at zero frequency (as illustrated in Fig. 2(c) in [52]), the direct components in the DFT domain can therefore be estimated.
4. Perform IDFT for the obtained harmonic frequency spectrum after nulling operation in procedure 3. The desired direct components can be obtained (as presented in Fig. 2(d) in [52]).

Perform procedures 1-4 for each measured field angle ϕ , and the direct components can be estimated.

$$\Theta(\phi) = |E_1(\phi)|^2 + |E_2(\phi)|^2 + |E_3(\phi)|^2 + |\sigma(\phi)|^2 \tag{5-9}$$

where $|\sigma(\phi)|^2$ is the interference power component due to the the spectrum leakages of the harmonic terms and is also the error source of the proposed method. Note that the scenario with $L = 3$ propagation paths is only chosen as an example, and the extension to a more generic multipath propagation environment is straightforward and doable. By using equations (9) and (10) in [52]), (5-9) can be represented as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Theta(\phi) &= \sum_{l=1}^L |E_l(\phi)|^2 + |\sigma(\phi)|^2 \\
&= \sum_{l=1}^L a_l^2 \cdot |A(\phi - \phi_l)|^2 + |\sigma(\phi)|^2 \\
&= \sum_{l=1}^L g_l \cdot T(\phi - \phi_l) + |\sigma(\phi)|^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5-10}$$

Actually, (5-10) is a circular convolution of $\sum_{l=1}^L g_l \delta(\phi - \phi_l)$ and $T(\phi)$ as:

$$\Theta(\phi) = T(\phi) * G(\phi) + |\sigma(\phi)|^2 \tag{5-11}$$

with

$$T(\phi) = |A(\phi)|^2 \tag{5-12}$$

$$G(\phi) = \sum_{l=1}^L a_l^2 \delta(\phi - \phi_l) \tag{5-13}$$

By performing DFT to (5-11) in the rotation angle domain, we obtain:

$$\tilde{\Theta} = \tilde{T} \cdot \tilde{G} + \tilde{\sigma} \tag{5-14}$$

$\tilde{\sigma}$ is the interference term $|\sigma(\phi)|^2$ in the DFT domain. As it was discussed when explaining the second method (i.e. the reference antenna method), a reference antenna to obtain the chamber response characteristic \tilde{G} (i.e. the environment factor) can be used. More specifically, $\Theta_{AUT}(\phi)$ and $\Theta_{REF}(\phi)$ are assumed to be the extracted direct components for each rotation angle from the AnUT and reference antenna measurement, respectively, where $T_{REF}(\phi)$ is the known power pattern of the reference antenna. Therefore, the environment factor can be obtained via element-wise division:

$$\tilde{G} = \tilde{\Theta}_{REF} / \tilde{T}_{REF} \tag{5-15}$$

Therefore, the AnUT power pattern in the DFT domain \tilde{T}_{AUT} can be estimated via element-wise division as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{T}_{AUT} &= \tilde{\Theta}_{AUT} / \tilde{G} \\
&= \frac{\tilde{\Theta}_{AUT} \tilde{T}_{REF}}{\tilde{\Theta}_{REF}}
\end{aligned} \tag{5-16}$$

Afterwards, by performing IDFT for \tilde{T}_{AUT} and take the square root, the antenna gain pattern $|A_{AUT}(\phi)|$ is recovered. The reason, the DFT procedure is performed, is the error analysis. The investigation in the DFT domain provides an insight into the undesired interference component, helping us to investigate the algorithm error and derive the guideline of the virtual array design.

5.3 Numerical analysis: reliable region, reference antenna selection, zero-frequency pollution, required length of probe movement, number of probe positions (probe spacing) and robustness

A non-anechoic environment is simulated in [52]) to study the performance and robustness of the proposed method. The measurement frequency is set to 28 GHz. An omnidirectional antenna is used as the probe positioned in the ϕ_1 direction. In addition to the LOS propagation ($a_1 = 1(0 \text{ dB})$ and $\phi_1 = 0^\circ$), two reflection waves with $a_2 = 0.5(-6 \text{ dB})$ and $\phi_2 = -40^\circ$ and $a_3 = 0.3(-10.5 \text{ dB})$ and $\phi_3 = -25^\circ$ are introduced to mimic the non-anechoic environment. As the AnUT, a horn antenna with HPBW of 20° is used. Two types of synthetic radiation patterns, i. e. specified by the 3GPP in [73], with HPBW of 20° (antenna A) and 40° (antenna B), respectively, are used as the reference antenna for the proposed technique. The synthetic pattern, flowchart of the simulation framework and comparison of the patterns are shown respectively in Fig. 3, Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 in [52]). By using the proposed echo suppression with reference antenna A, it is shown that the radiation pattern is successfully recovered, in terms of the pattern shape, HPBW, and gain. In practical applications, the environment or measurement system would introduce noise. Therefore, the complex random noise was added to the simulated measurement, with the SNR chosen to be 40 dB, and the Monte Carlo simulation with 1000 realizations was performed. Reference antenna A was used in this simulation. For the most realizations, the results similar to the presented in Fig. 5 in [52] could be obtained. However, in some extreme cases, noticeable errors may occur in weak signal directions (far from the main lobe direction in the antenna pattern). This would be expected, because weak signals are more sensitive to noise, compared to the main beam region.

Further, the reader is advised to review Fig. 6 - Fig. 14 in [52], where a detailed analysis on the reconstructed patterns is discussed and presented. The comparison between the true and the reconstructed AnUT power patterns, with and without noise, in the DFT domain, and all the curves match to a good extend within the reliable region. However, significant deviations were found outside the reliable region in the case with noise. The components referred to as the spurious components, presented considerable power. Actually, the spurious components are the main cause of the deteriorated performance, because the other high-frequency components, deviating from the target, contribute a bit to the pattern, because of their negligible power. However, this problem can be solved by applying a rectangular window for the obtained pattern in the DFT domain, i.e. by gating the components outside the reliable region, the recovered pattern (shown as the blue curve in Fig. 6(a) in [52]) is significantly improved.

The proposed strategy is examined by comparing the results using the reference antenna A and those for using the reference antenna B (antenna B has a larger HPBW compared to the AUT). It was found that the proposed algorithm with reference antenna B would not work. Moreover, gating operation would not help improving the results. It is well known fact that a less directional antenna will have a narrower main lobe in the DFT domain. The latter leads to narrower reliable region (reference antenna B). Therefore, the spurious components in the AnUT DFT pattern appears in the position close to 0° , which can not be filtered by gating. The main conclusion is that the reliable region of the reference antenna must be broader than that of the AnUT. In other words, the reference antenna must be more (or at least equally) directional than the AnUT.

The harmonic components in (5-8) should be ideally delta-shape impulse responses in the DFT domain. However, they are not, because of the finite length of the power measurement sequence from the virtual probe array. Therefore, the power leakage in the frequency spectrum is not avoidable and will result in interfering power on the zero frequency in the DFT domain, introducing undesired components $\tilde{\sigma}$ to $\tilde{\Theta}$. The interfering power introduced by the spectrum leakage is referred to as zero-frequency pollution. We discuss how zero-frequency pollution would affect the proposed algorithm and how to mitigate the adverse effects (reference antenna A is used). The spectrum leakage is determined by the length of the processed power sequence. Therefore, the longer the length of the power sequence, the less leakage will be introduced [74]. However, longer sequence length means also more measurement locations and longer measurement time. Two configurations are considered here, i.e. case α : 15 probe positions and case β : 30 probe positions. The same moving step $\Delta d = \lambda$ is used. Fig. 8 in [52] presents the results. It was observed a noticeable accuracy deterioration for configuration α compared to that with $M = 30$ probe positions. This phenomenon can be explained by looking at the individual harmonic frequency spectrum of all the components in (5-8) at a certain field angle. As it was expected, the components in the DFT domain act in the form of the sinc function [74]. When the larger sampling length is adopted, all the components in the harmonic frequency spectrum become closer to the Dirac impulse, and less zero-frequency pollution will be introduced. Therefore, using a large virtual probe array for the proposed algorithm is important to reduce the zero-frequency pollution and improve the recovery precision.

If the length of probe movement is D , the spatial BW is $1/D$. \tilde{k} is assumed to be the minimum harmonic frequency A . D should satisfy the relationship:

$$D > \frac{2}{\tilde{k}} \quad (5-17)$$

Equation (5-17) shows a practical guideline for the required distance of the probe movement. However, \tilde{k} is typically unknown. The selection of D depends on the differences in the impinging angle of propagation paths. A large separation would need a small D . If the roughly estimation of the dominant echoes in the environment is possible, then the D can be set accordingly.

Moving the probe to many locations will typically require long measurement time. Therefore, we will derive the relationship between the number of probe positions and the precision of the algorithm. From the main principle of the Fourier transform, it is known that the length of the sequence determines the lobe width and decaying rate of the sinc function in the DFT domain. On the other hand, for a fixed sequence length, the number of sampling points, i.e., sampling rate, determines the spectrum aliasing in the DFT domain. With given probe movement length D , the sampling rate is $f_s = (M - 1)/D$. k' is assumed to be the maximum harmonic frequency in (5-8). All signal processing algorithms would satisfy the Nyquist sampling theorem to avoid spectrum aliasing in the DFT domain. However, the proposed method is concerned with zero-frequency fidelity, and the aliasing at other frequency points is not significant. Fig. 12 in [52] presents an example of the harmonic spectrum and the periodically extended spectrum introduced by the finite Fourier transform (the Hamming window is used). It could be observed that although the spectrum aliasing exists, the zero-frequency point is not impacted as well. Therefore, a criteria that the sampling rate should follow:

$$f_s > k' + B \quad (5-18)$$

or after some transformations:

$$\begin{aligned} M &= f_s D + 1 > (k' + B) D + 1 \\ &= k' D + B D + 1 \\ &= k' D + 3. \end{aligned} \tag{5-19}$$

During a long measurement (especially when considering the phase measurement), the chamber environment may normally not remain stationary. Therefore, the phases of propagation paths are not stable. However, the spatial deconvolution (as discussed in the second section) would require an accurate phase information. Fig. 14 in [52] presents the recovered patterns for 200 realizations with the conventional spatial deconvolution algorithm and the proposed algorithm, using the data with and without phase noise. The unstable phase was modeled by adding small random phase deviations ranging from -3.6° to 3.6° . In this simulation, $D = 60\lambda$, $\phi_1 = -28^\circ$, $\phi_2 = -25^\circ$, and ten probe positions are used. It can be observed that in the ideal scenario, the reference method presents excellent accuracy, while the performance significantly deteriorates, when the measurement environment is changed, even for a rather small phase variation. However, the proposed method is relatively not susceptible to the unstable phases, especially in the main beam and first sidelobe regions. It can be concluded that the phase deviations are associated with the impacts of zero-frequency pollution and pseudo path, leading to variations of the recovered pattern.

5.4 Experimental validation

The measurements are conducted in a large AC at Aalborg University, Aalborg, Denmark. The test scenario is presented in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Experimental setup in a non-anechoic scenario

A metal plate with the size of $1\text{ m} \times 1\text{ m}$ is used to construct a non-anechoic environment. The plate location is configured to create strong reflection paths towards the probe. The probe and the AnUT used LGF-11-1800-WB-DL

antenna with HPBW of 40° , as presented in Figure 18a. A standard gain horn (SGH) antenna Flann 22240-20 with HPBW of 20° (Figure 18b) was employed as the reference antenna. The measurement frequency was 28 GHz and λ_b was the wavelength.

Figure 18: Photos of (a) probe (AnUT) antenna and (b) reference antennas

The implementation of the virtual probe array in the validation measurement can be summarized by the following steps:

- 1) Place the reference antenna (with a known pattern) on the turntable.
- 2) Move the probe antenna to the first spatial location, where the distance from the probe to the reference antenna (or AnUT) is 9.22 m in our measurement setup.
- 3) The reference antenna is rotated in the azimuth plane and measured for the first spatial location.
- 4) Repeat the antenna pattern measurement for probe antenna at other spatial locations (with the help of a slider) and obtain the received power response of reference antenna $P_{REF}(m, \phi)$ for all spatial locations, i.e., (10). The movement direction is along the LOS path propagation. In our measurement, the probe is moved to $M = 38$ points with $\Delta d = 0.5\lambda_b$ covering the 19.82 – cm measurement range.
- 5) Replace the reference antenna with AnUT. Repeat the procedures (1)–(4) for the AnUT to obtain the received power response of AnUT $P_{AUT}(m, \phi)$ for all spatial locations, i.e. (5-8).

A single measurement (at one probe position) of the AnUT pattern or the reference antenna pattern in a 2-D azimuth plane takes only one minute. The power divergence of the propagation path among the probe array introduced by the FSPL is not more than 0.18 dB and it can be ignored. To examine the environment characteristics, the AnUT is rotated and the frequency responses at the frequency band 28–30 GHz by using a VNA are measured. For each angle, 101 frequency points are recorded. Note that the wideband complex-signal measurement aims to show the power angle delay profile (PADP) of the employed non-anechoic environment, while for the proposed algorithm only single-frequency amplitude-only data at 28 GHz is used. Figure 19 presents the results for the obtained PADP.

Figure 19: PADPs of (a) anechoic and (b) NAC environments

Except the LOS path and reflection, there are also some weaker propagation paths, as indicated by the yellow arrow, which may be caused by system nonideality, the scattering path caused by the setup components, and the diffraction paths introduced by the edges of the plate. It is observed that a path appears with a delay smaller than that of the LOS. It is a signal path that should be introduced by the loose connector behind the probe antenna or insufficient isolation between the Transmitter (Tx) and the Rx. Furthermore, it can be concluded that the diffraction paths may be not only from 2-D plane, but also in the 3-D direction, due to the top and bottom edges of the plate. Note that the presented results are without normalization to demonstrate the agreement between the reconstructed and the true antenna patterns.

For the algorithm validation, the reference antenna and AnUT are first measured in the AC and then measured at 28 GHz in the constructed non-anechoic environment for the preset 38 probe positions. The antenna patterns measured in a NAC are presented in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Reconstructed patterns using different sets of probe positions

The red curve indicates that due to the multipath interference, -20-dB gain deviations are introduced in the region around -30° . Furthermore, the gain, HPBW, and location of the main beam can not be accurately measured. By applying the proposed processing algorithm, Figure 20 illustrates that a significant improvement of the antenna pattern can be achieved, and the amplitude of the main beam is well recovered. Slight deviations at the angles about -100° can be caused by MU and zero-frequency pollutions. Additionally, marginal discrepancy appears in the regions of $\varphi = -130^\circ$ to 180° and 130° to 180° , which is attributed to the low SNRs in these regions in the measurement.

To examine the inference about the required numbers of probe positions, different sets of probes are employed for algorithm validation. The maximum harmonic frequency is assumed to be contributed by the echo from -45° and the LOS path. The derived number should be larger than 8.4 positions when applying the window function. Thus, the probe position index with the spacing of 2, 3, and 4 is selected, i.e., the index $[1, 3, 5, \dots, 37]$ ($M = 19$), $[1, 4, 7, \dots, 37]$ ($M = 13$), and $[1, 5, 9, \dots, 37]$ ($M = 10$), respectively, to perform the proposed algorithm. The recovered results are shown in Figure 20, and the excellent matches validated the effectiveness of the proposed criteria, and the peak deviation is only 0.2 dB. Figure 19 shows that the reflection path is actually at approximately -28° . The derived required number of probe locations is $M = 5.1$, and at least six locations should be used. As expected, when $M = 5$, obvious pattern distortions can be observed in Figure 20. The obtained minimum length of probe movement for the algorithm implementation is $\hat{D} = 0.183$ m. Figure 21 shows the patterns reconstructed with the lengths of $100\%\hat{D}$, $75\%\hat{D}$, $50\%\hat{D}$, and $25\%\hat{D}$.

Figure 21: Reconstructed pattern using different sets of probe positions

As the movement length decreases, larger deviations are introduced. However, the main lobe and gain can still be well obtained with more than $50\% \hat{D}$. It is because though zero-frequency pollution is introduced, its contribution is not too significant, leading to marginal effects.

The MU of the extracted radiation pattern and accuracy of the deviation from the ideal pattern is mainly given by the measurement setup imperfections. The MU of the radiation pattern main lobe amplitude measured using a VNA at the frequency 30 GHz is typically ± 0.1 dB and the MU of side lobes can vary from ± 0.3 dB to ± 0.7 dB depending on the lobe amplitude. Since long measurement cables are employed and the probe antenna is moved to different locations, one has to take into account the amplitude and phase stability of the cables due to flexure. For quality 3.5mm cables with length of 2 meters, the amplitude instability is typically ± 0.3 dB and the phase instability is typically $\pm 6^\circ$ at the frequency 30 GHz. If longer cables are used, even higher instability can be expected with flexure. The temperature changes influence the phase stability of cables as well. As shown above, the selection of time-domain window and other numerical aspects may also influence the amplitude of the reconstructed radiation pattern. However, these effects are much smaller than the influence of hardware imperfections.

5.5 Conclusion

In this subchapter, a novel echo suppression method with a single-frequency phase-less measurement is suggested to recover the antenna gain pattern measured in the NAC. In order to perform the proposed method, firstly, the pattern measurement for a known reference antenna is conducted to extract the multipath characteristics (chamber environment). Secondly, the measurement is repeated for the AnUT, and then the true antenna pattern of the AnUT is re-

covered by compensating the multipath characteristics (obtained with the measurement with the reference antenna). The simulation and measurement results demonstrate the excellent performance of the proposed method for antenna measurement. Compared to the other pattern reconstruction algorithms in a non-anechoic measurement, the proposed method recovers the true AnUT pattern with single-frequency power-only (phase-less) data. Detailed analysis and systematic guidelines are provided for the proposed echo suppression method. To further reduce the required measurement length, one can develop an improved processing method to extract the clean direct components in (10), which can be an assignment for future research. The feasibility of the proposed algorithms for 2- D antenna measurement was demonstrated. In future investigations, the 3-D spatial deconvolution principle to recover the 3-D antenna pattern can be exploited.

6. An Efficient Multi-Beam Pattern Measurement Campaign for Millimeter-Wave Phased Arrays

6.1 Introduction

The ability of mmWave phased arrays to produce a beam of radio waves that can be electronically directed in various directions has led to their widespread use in mmWave communication systems [75]. According to 3GPP specifications, 5G mmWave UE and BS devices with integrated AiP designs must undergo an OTA compliance test [76], [77], [5]. A detailed characterization of the device's performance under FF conditions is required for the testing. The performance of radio systems is largely dependent on the antenna pattern and its essential parameters, such as the main beam, sidelobes, and nulls. Additionally, the knowledge of antenna array element pattern can help with the design and development of phased arrays. Conventional antenna pattern measurements with different antenna ranges [78], [79], [80], [8], [81] have been well investigated in the literature. These measurements are inefficient for multi-beam measurements of mmWave beam-steerable phased arrays [82]. A fast multi-beam pattern reconstruction technique for mmWave phased arrays has been proposed in [82]. Based on the measured element patterns, the suggested approach may quickly reconstruct the phased array's multi-beam patterns. The suggested method retrieves the element pattern in the typical all-on operating mode of phased arrays, which is when all elements are excited, as opposed to the traditional element pattern measurement, which involves the individual excitation of each element (i.e., in an on-off mode). In [83], an orthogonal code-based measuring method is used to concurrently collect all element patterns in a hybrid beamforming array. The measuring system must incorporate an additional pulse generator with multiprobe for coding, which is more complex than traditional antenna measurement facilities. More significantly, only digital and hybrid beamformed arrays can use the technique in [83] since it necessitates separate array element ports that are connected to the pulse generator. [84] reported similar work, although it only applies to antenna systems with digital beamformer structure. While the principle of reference [82] can be directly applied to digital and hybrid structures, it focuses on pattern measuring techniques that are applicable to analog structures in contrast to [83].

The work provided in [85], which forms the basis of the content in this subchapter, carries out an effective multi-beam pattern measuring campaign for mmWave phased arrays, based on [82].

6.2 Measurement setup and procedure

A 4x4 mmWave phased array AiP, as described in [86], was used in the measurement campaign. A measurement experiment in this study confirmed the multi-beam pattern measurement approach reported in [82] using a typical CATR setup at Aalborg University, Aalborg, Denmark. The frequency bands for the AiP and CATR setups are 26.5 GHz to 29.5 GHz and 6 GHz to 60 GHz, respectively. The CATR setup primarily consists of a reflector, a feed antenna, an AC, and a turntable. Figure 22 displays the measurement setup made up of the AiP and the CATR setup.

Figure 22: A photo of measurement setup in a CATR chamber. The VNA and a computer installed with the control program are outside the chamber

The AiP was positioned in the QZ of the CATR setup, where the FF plane wave condition is satisfied, with the polarization of feed antenna and AiP aligned. The transmission S-parameter measurements between the feed antenna port and the AiP port were conducted via a VNA. With the AiP operating in receive mode, the transmit and receive ports of VNA were connected to the feed antenna port and the AiP port, respectively. The S parameters in different FF observation directions of the AiP were recorded with the AiP rotation in the CATR setup. Traditionally, the S-parameters that are directly monitored in the on-off mode and the all-on mode, respectively, were used to record the array and element patterns. However, in the suggested technique in [82], the element pattern was retrieved without turning on and off elements by using the S-parameters measured in the all-on mode. As it is shown in Figure 22, the AiP antenna configuration is a 4×4 URA made up of 4 horizontal 1×4 ULAs distributed vertically. Using seven beams with horizontal beam-steering angles of 0° , $\pm 17^\circ$, $\pm 35^\circ$, and $\pm 59^\circ$ as an example, the ULA indicated in Figure 22 and URA were separately examined in the subsequent measurement campaign.

6.2.1 Conventional pattern measurement method Traditionally, in the standard CATR setup, the AiP element pattern and array pattern were directly measured at 28 GHz. The AiP was rotated horizontally with an azimuth angle ranging from -90° to 90° using a constant step of 1° . The azimuth angle of 0° indicated the AiP position in Figure 22 with the broadside direction pointing to the CATR reflector center. A horizontal pattern cut across azimuth angles inside $[-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ has been captured once AiP has finished its full horizontal rotation. Using the traditional on-off measured element patterns, the 4 and 16 element patterns in the ULA and URA without beam-steering were measured directly, with one element being activated and the rest deactivated each time. In the all-on mode of both arrays steered to seven beams (i.e., 0° , $\pm 17^\circ$, $\pm 35^\circ$, and $\pm 59^\circ$), the target array patterns for comparison were monitored directly.

6.2.2 Proposed pattern measurement method The suggested pattern measurement uses the same system hardware as the traditional measurement. However, the AiP was rotated horizontally with an azimuth angle from -90° to 90° in a constant step of 5° . Five and seventeen S-parameter measurements for five and seventeen additional phase shift settings of elements according to [82] were made for the ULA and URA, respectively, assuming that AiP elements had initial phase shift settings of 0° at each azimuth angle. The element patterns measured in the all-on mode, or the suggested all-on measured element pattern, were measured following the completion of the S-parameter measurements for all azimuth angles. The all-on reconstructed array patterns were created by adding up the all-on measured element patterns with and without beam-steering weights for the steered beams ($\pm 17^\circ$, $\pm 35^\circ$, and $\pm 59^\circ$) and the broadside beam (0°), respectively. Likewise, the traditionally measured on-off element patterns are added up to form the on-off reconstructed array patterns. For validation, the target array patterns measured in the traditional measurement were compared with the on-off and all-on reconstructed array patterns.

6.3 Measurement results

Figure 23 presents the on-off and all-on measured element patterns for both arrays with an angle step of 5° .

Figure 23: Element patterns measured in the on-off and all-on modes for both arrays

Since the ULA is made from the URA, the on-off measured element patterns are the same for both arrays. Therefore, the common elements in both arrays (i.e., element index 9, 10, 11, 12 indicated in Figure 22) are examined. In contrast to simulations, the element patterns in both arrays are not smooth. The effects of amplifiers and element coupling in active phased arrays may be among the reasons. Compared to the URA, the element patterns measured

in the ULA's on-off and all-on modes match more closely. One explanation is that because the number of activated elements varies across the ULA and URA arrays, the AiP chip temperature may fluctuate as well. The ULA with four activated elements has a chip temperature of around 40°C, which is comparable to the ULA with one activated element (i.e., the on-off mode), whereas the URA with sixteen activated elements has a temperature of about 100°C. As mentioned in [86], the temperature has an impact on the amplifier response in element branches. Consequently, with an active phased array AiP, the element patterns observed in the on-off and all-on modes may differ. As the array scale increases, the difference will get larger.

The power patterns of the ULA and URA for 7 beams are shown in Figure 24 and in Figure 25, respectively. While the on-off reconstructed array patterns only match the target for the ULA, the all-on reconstructed array patterns match the target array patterns for both arrays in terms of main beam direction and power. For instance, the primary beam peak direction for the URA broadside beam shows a 1.5-dB amplitude error between the target and on-off reconstructed array patterns. The necessity of measuring element patterns in an all-on mode for effective multi-beam measurement is highlighted by the finding that the on-off reconstructed array pattern is not the actual array pattern in the all-on working mode for seven beams.

Figure 24: ULA pattern comparison between the target and the reconstructed for 7 beams a) 0° b) -17° c) 17° d) -35° e) 35° f) -59° and g) 59°

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

Figure 25: URA pattern comparison between the target and the reconstructed for 7 beams a) 0° b) -17° c) 17° d) -35° e) 35° f) -59° and g) 59°

The number of sampling angles within $[-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ is decreased from 181 points with a uniform step of 1° to 19 points with a uniform step of 10° and to 7 points with a uniform step of 30° in order to better illustrate the effectiveness of the measurement campaign. The number of mechanical rotations needed in the current hardware configuration or the number of probes needed in a multi-probe arrangement can both be decreased by lowering the number of sampling angles. The URA, for instance, is sampled with an angle step of 10° and 30° to produce the all-on measured element patterns, which are then interpolated with an angle step of 1° . Ultimately, different array patterns are reconstructed with an angle step of 1° by combining the interpolated element patterns and the beam-steering weights from different beams. For beams 0° , -17° , -35° , and -59° , respectively. The array patterns reconstructed by 10° and 30° angle sampling steps are compared with the target array pattern with an angle step of 1° in Figure 26.

Figure 26: URA pattern comparison between the target and the all-on reconstructed using two element pattern sampling steps for 4 beams a) 0° b) -17° c) -35° and d) -59°

Although there is an error in terms of sidelobes and nulls, the two angle sampling stages produce the same main beam pattern as the target for four beams. Compared to 30° sampling, the sidelobe and null errors obtained by 10° sampling are smaller. Note that depending on the application, a trade-off between the pattern accuracy and the sparse sampling step should be taken into account. For instance, in mmWave UE applications, where sparse angle sampling can be used, the primary beam is the focus. The sampling step will be lowered for more accurate pattern performance in applications like mmWave BS where precise measurements of sidelobes and nulls are required.

6.4 Conclusion

Using a fast multi-beam pattern measuring technique of mmWave phased array antenna systems, an effective multi-beam pattern measurement campaign has been described. For multi-beam pattern reconstruction of phased arrays, it is possible to precisely extract all element complex patterns in the practical all-on mode of arrays throughout the measurement campaign. Furthermore, a sparse sample of element patterns with a wide beamwidth can more effectively reconstruct the multi-beam array patterns. Extending the measuring technique based on a NF setup with a shorter measurement distance would be ideal for future research. The free space propagation coefficients between array elements and probes need to be carefully calibrated out from the measured element fields. Due to the inaccessible antenna connectors and the difficulties of phase measurement at mmWave frequencies, the requirement for complex measurement may be challenging. Therefore, in practical mmWave systems, it would be also preferable to retrieve the element complex pattern by amplitude-only measurements.

7. AC Direct Far-field (FF) Measurements of Total Radiated Power (TRP)

7.1 Scope

This chapter shows results for an anechoic-chamber-based method for the measurement of TRP from 5G BSs in the FR2 frequency range (39 GHz). The 5G NR FR2 signal at 39 GHz was generated by a vector signal transceiver (VST) NI PXIe-5840, together with mixers to upconvert and down-convert IF signal at 3.5 GHz into 39 GHz. All measurements were performed at the NPL SMART chamber facility in Teddington, United Kingdom. The measurements were performed as a part of Activity A1.2.5 in the 21NRM03 MEWS project.

7.2 Introduction

In 5G NR, especially in FR2, radio systems integrate the antenna array with the RF front-end, making it difficult to perform conducted power measurement. Beamforming and direction-dependent antenna gain also cause large variations in radiated power that cannot be captured at a connector port. Therefore, 3GPP defines transmitter performance using TRP, which represents the spatially averaged power radiated into free space. TRP enables consistent OTA evaluation across different antenna architectures and ensures that minimum output power, spurious emissions, and other transmitter requirements reflect real-world radiated behavior rather than internal RFIC characteristics. The NR System Simulator (SS) and the DUT shall be configured in accordance with TS 38.521-1 [87], Section 6.2.1 (UE maximum output power), using the default settings defined in TS 38.521-1 [87] and TS 38.508-1 [88] as applicable. The measurement shall be performed based on the detailed test parameters specified for each band in Table 4.3.3-1 of TR 38.834 [89].

Meanwhile, in mm-wave FR2 testing, OTA measurements face a major imbalance between downlink (DL) and uplink (UL) power levels. Due to very large free-space path loss at millimeter-wave frequencies, the transmit power in UL becomes extremely weak, often approaching the noise floor, making reliable EIRP/TRP measurement difficult. Conversely, DL signaling from the test equipment must be strong enough to maintain link stability, which can drive the UE receiver into saturation during EIS sensitivity tests. This “high-DL / low-UL” mismatch leads to measurement dynamic-range limitations, receiver overload, excessive attenuation requirements, poor SNR in UL, and unreliable OTA results, motivating the need for near-field methods, hybrid FF/NF techniques to maintain the test feasibility.

7.3 3GPP’s definition of Total Radiated Power with Anechoic Chamber Method

Transmitter power measurements shall be performed using TRP as a measurement metric. This definition will be used to calculate the TRP value of NR FR1 DUT where the TRP with AC method is defined as:

$$\text{TRP} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{\theta=0}^{\pi} \int_{\phi=0}^{2\pi} (\text{EIRP}_{\theta}(\theta, \phi) + \text{EIRP}_{\phi}(\theta, \phi)) \sin \theta \, d\phi \, d\theta. \quad (7-1)$$

where the effective isotropic radiated power (EIRP) is defined as:

$$\text{EIRP}(\theta, \phi) = P_T G_T(\theta, \phi). \quad (7-2)$$

where is the product of the power delivered to the antenna P_T and the antenna’s power gain G_T . Note that EIRP_{θ} and EIRP_{ϕ} denote the EIRP components in the corresponding θ - and ϕ -polarizations. The discrete forms of

angle interval in the θ - and ϕ -directions are represented by $\Delta\phi = \frac{2\pi}{M}$ and $\Delta\theta = \frac{\pi}{N}$, respectively. Therefore, the discrete summation form of TRP for the AC method, using the $\sin\theta\Delta\theta$ weighting, is expressed as [90]:

$$\text{TRP} \approx \frac{\pi}{2NM} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} (\text{EIRP}_{\theta}(\theta_n, \phi_m) + \text{EIRP}_{\phi}(\theta_n, \phi_m)) \sin\theta_n. \quad (7-3)$$

where N and M are the number of sampling intervals for θ and ϕ axes, respectively. θ_n and ϕ_m are the measurement angles. In theory, there is no singularity or loss of information at the pole ($\theta = 0^\circ$), because the polar axis corresponds to a single point with zero solid angle, and the integration is mathematically well-defined. However, in practical numerical integration, the radiation pattern is sampled at discrete θ values, typically at uniform angular steps such as 1° , 2° , or 5° . If the maximum radiation beam is directed exactly toward $\theta = 0^\circ$, two following problems may occur:

1. The measurement points at $\theta = 0^\circ$ have a weight of $\sin\theta = 0$, resulting in zero contribution to TRP calculation in (7-3).
2. The next available sampling point (e.g., $\theta = 15^\circ$) may already be significantly below the actual peak level, especially for highly directive millimeter-wave antennas.

As a result, the discrete approximation may underestimate the radiated power in the vicinity of the main beam. To solve this problem, the Clenshaw-Curtis quadrature may be used in the integral instead. The summation form based on the Clenshaw-Curtis quadrature integral approximation of TRP with AC method is defined as:

$$\text{TRP} \approx \frac{1}{2M} \sum_{n=0}^N \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} (\text{EIRP}_{\theta}(\theta_n, \phi_m) + \text{EIRP}_{\phi}(\theta_n, \phi_m)) W(\theta_n). \quad (7-4)$$

where the value of $W(\theta_n)$ follows Table 1 below (Table 5.1-1 in TR 38.834 [89]).

Table 1: Weights for Clenshaw–Curtis Quadrature with $\Delta\theta = 15^\circ$.

Clenshaw–Curtis	
θ [deg.]	Weights
0	0.0070
15	0.0661
30	0.1315
45	0.1848
60	0.2270
75	0.2527
90	0.2620
105	0.2527
120	0.2270
135	0.1848
150	0.1315
165	0.0661
180	0.0070

7.4 Far-Field DL Testbed Implementation inside AC

Figure 27 shows the measurement system configuration developed for evaluating the TRP or effective isotropic radiated power (EIRP) in the millimetre-wave frequency range. The antenna under test (Tx) is mounted on a rotatable positioner inside an anechoic chamber, which allows both azimuth and elevation scanning. This enables the acquisition of the radiated power distribution in all spatial directions, from which the TRP is calculated by spatial integration. The chamber walls are covered with RF absorbers to suppress reflections and to emulate free-space conditions. A receiving antenna (Rx) with known gain value is fixed at a specific position to detect the electromagnetic waves radiated from the Tx antenna.

Figure 27: FR2 TRP OTA test system implemented in our study for 38.5 GHz band; AMP: amplifier, MX: mixer, DCP: directional coupler, PDV: power divider, SG: signal generator

In the transmit and receive signal paths, a set of high-frequency amplifiers, band-pass filters, and frequency mixers are used for frequency conversion and unwanted signal suppression. The millimeter-wave LO signal at 35 GHz (output power: 4 dBm) is generated by an LO signal generator (Rohde and Schwarz, SMB100B). Because coaxial-cable loss at 35 GHz is significantly higher than in the microwave region below 18 GHz, the LO generator is placed inside the chamber to minimize cable length and reduce transmission loss for the common LO distribution. The LO signal is then amplified by an amplifier (Agilent, 83050A, 2–50 GHz) and delivered through a power divider (Mini-Circuits, ZC2PD-5R263-S+) to two 10-dB directional couplers (Mini-Circuits, ZCDC10-5R263-S+) to increase isolation and suppress leakage RF signals from the transmitter path to the receiver path. The LO signals fed from the directional couplers are up-converted to 38.5 GHz by a mixer (Mini-Circuits, ZMDB-653H-E+) using a 3.5-GHz baseband IF signal with a bandwidth of 40 MHz generated by an VST NI PXIe-5840. The resulting 38.5-GHz RF signal is amplified by a power amplifier (ERZIA, ERZ-HPA-2400-5000-28) and then passed through a cavity band-pass filter (Aaren Technology, AT22F-WS422-KF) before being transmitted to the antenna under test (AUT). On the receiving side, the signal captured by a well-calibrated Rx antenna (A-Info, LB-180400-15-C-KF) is amplified by a low-noise amplifier (ERZIA, ERZ-LNA-2600-4000-30-2.5) and filtered using a cavity band-pass filter (Aaren Technology, AT22F-WS422-KF) before being down-converted to an intermediate frequency

(IF) by the mixer (Mini Circuits, ZMDB-653H-E+). The resulting IF signal at 3.5 GHz is then amplified by an amplifier (Agilent, 83020A) and goes through an LTCC lowpass filter (Mini Circuits, DC - 3800 MHz). Finally, the signal is digitized by an NI PXIe-5840 VST, which performs integrated I/Q demodulation, frequency sweeping, and power computation.

This system enables broadband and highly accurate radiated power measurements in the millimeter-wave band and is suitable for characterizing the radiation performance of 5G/6G wireless terminals and antenna modules.

7.5 Measurement Procedure of Receiver Path Loss

According to the procedure stated in TR 38.834 [89], the relative power values of the measurement points will be transformed to absolute radiated power values (in dBm) by performing a range path loss measurement. The DUT is placed at the center of the QZ inside the chamber, and the attenuation of the complete receiver path, L_{total} , from the receiving antenna end to the measurement receiver should be calibrated out beforehand. Firstly, direct connection between the end of the cable at the transmitter side to that of the receiver side inside the chamber is done as shown in Figure 28 and the power at the output of the cable at the transmitter side is then measured.

Figure 28: Measurement of receiver path loss L_{total} ; AMP: amplifier, MX: mixer, DCP: directional coupler, PDV: power divider, SG: signal generator

A conventional RF and microwave power meter measures the total in-band power integrated over the entire occupied signal bandwidth, rather than the power at individual frequency components. Since typical power meters employ thermoelectric or diode-based sensing without frequency-selective filtering, all signal components entering the sensor within its specified operating frequency range are summed to produce a single average power value. Figure 29 shows the receiving signal at the VST when the total in-band power at the end of the transmitter side is equal to -26.88 dBm, -37.08 dBm, -47.09 dBm, and -57.10 dBm, respectively.

Figure 29: Measurement of received power at the receiver in the IF band

The band-integrated average powers measured at the receiver or VST for four cases, i.e., without attenuator, with 10 dB, 20 dB, and 30 dB attenuator, are equal to -6.33 dBm, -13.14 dBm, -22.58 dBm, and -32.41 dBm, respectively. Figure 30 shows the relationship between the measured power at the cable end and the received power at the VST. Figure 30 indicates the linear relationship between the received power at the receiver and the input power measured at the cable end. The data points align closely with the fitted straight line, indicating a high degree of linearity when the input power is below around -40 dBm. The slope of the fitted line represents the proportionality factor between the input and output power. Finally, we can determine the path loss at the receiver side by subtracting the received power with the input power which lies in the linear range, i.e., $L_{cable} = P_{meas} - P_T = -32.41 - (-57.10) = 24.69 dB$. Since L_{cable} has a positive value, the receiving side experiences a gain rather than a loss since amplifiers were used in the receiving path.

Figure 30: Linearity between the input power measured at the cable end and the received power at the receiver

7.6 TRP Test Procedure

According to the TRP test procedure stated in TR 38.834 [89], the TRP of the DUT is measured by sampling the radiated transmit power of the DUT with a 3D scan at various locations surrounding the device. The measurement is performed with a constant sampling step of 15 degrees in both θ - and φ -direction for TRP measurement. As per 3GPP standard, number of sampling points in θ - and φ -direction are set to $N = 13$ and $M = 24$, respectively. This accounts for a total number of 312 measurements for each of two orthogonal components. All the measured power values will be integrated into TRP, as defined in Clause 5.1 of TR 38.834 [89]. The measurement procedure includes the following steps:

1. Place the DUT inside the QZ following the positioning guideline defined in Clause 6 of TR 38.834 [89].
2. Connect the NR SS with the DUT through the link antenna following Steps 1 and 2 in Section 6.2.1.4.2 of TS 38.521-1 [91] and ensure the DUT transmits with its maximum power.
3. Measure the power at each measurement point, and calculate EIRP(θ, φ) by subtracting the composite loss of the entire receiver path.

The TRP value is calculated using the TRP integration approaches outlined in Clause 5.1 in [92] and here described in Section 7.3.

7.7 TRP Measurement Results

The measured power results using VST in NPL are shown in Figure 31. The power measured at the VST can be converted into EIRP using the following equation:

$$P_{\text{meas}} [\text{dBm}] = P_T [\text{dBm}] + G_T [\text{dBi}] + G_R [\text{dBi}] + 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi d} \right) \text{ dB} + L_{\text{cable}} [\text{dB}]. \quad (7-5)$$

Therefore,

$$\text{EIRP} [\text{dBm}] = P_T + G_T = P_{\text{meas}} - G_R - 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi d} \right) - L_{\text{cable}}. \quad (7-6)$$

where P_T is the transmitting power supplied to the transmitting antenna, G_T and G_R are the transmitting and receiving antenna gains, respectively. P_{meas} is the power measured at the VST, λ is the wavelength, d is the distance between transmitting and receiving antennas. Here $d = 1.7$ m and $\lambda = 7.79\text{mm}$ at 38.5 GHz. L_{cable} represents the path loss of the receiver side from the end of the receiving cable to the VST, which is measured using procedures in subchapter 7.5. A standard gain horn antenna (Flann Microwave, Model no. 22240-20) with a typical gain of 20 dBi and a double-ridge guided horn antenna (A-Info, LB-180400-15-C-KF) with a typical gain of 15 dBi were used as transmitting and receiving antennas, respectively. From 31, the maximum receiving power of -63.66 dBm at 38.5 GHz for combined polarization is obtained when $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\varphi = 345^\circ$, which is slightly shifted from the boresight direction of the antenna. This may be caused by antenna misalignment. The EIRP at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\varphi = 345^\circ$ is calculated as:

$$\text{EIRP} = -63.66 \text{ dBm} - 17.22 \text{ dB} - (-68.76 \text{ dB}) - 24.69 \text{ dB} = -36.81 [\text{dBm}]. \quad (7-7)$$

Since PT measured at the cable end before connecting to the transmitting antenna is -58.52 dBm at 38.5 GHz, the transmitting antenna gain is then determined as 21.71 dBi. Meanwhile, the simulated antenna gain derived by using the

Method of Moment is 21.60 dBi. Consequently, the measurement and simulation results closely matched each other, confirming the validity of our measurement system.

Next, TRPs are calculated using (7-3) for uniform angular step and (7-4) when using the Clenshaw-Curtis quadrature in the integral approximation of TRP. For a uniform angular step of 15° , TRP = -53.55 dBm at 38.5 GHz while TRP = -54.10 dBm when using Clenshaw-Curtis quadrature. The difference between two methods is approximately 0.55 dB. This may be attributed to a large cap area used in approximating its contribution to the TRP near the pole where $\theta = 0^\circ$. When a uniform angular step of 9° is applied, TRP is determined as -54.27 dBm and the difference reduces to 0.17 dB when compared with that from the Clenshaw-Curtis quadrature method.

Figure 31: Measured power at the VST for (a) θ -polarization, (b) ϕ -polarization, and (c) combined polarization with number of measurement points aligned with 3GPP standards, i.e., $N = 13$ and $M = 24$.

7.8 Conclusion

In this chapter, we discuss the necessity of the TRP measurement for performance evaluation in 5G NR FR2 band, where conducted measurements are difficult to carry out due to antenna-RF-front-end integration and beamforming function. Since the 5G NR FR2 frequency is much higher than those in the FR1, there are many challenges in FR2 OTA testing, such as higher cable losses and signals becoming extremely weak due to such loss, while strong DL signal may encounter risks of receiver saturation. Fundamentals in the TRP measurement method using a uniform angular step and the Clenshaw-Curtis quadrature are given in detail. Measurement system using VST, developed in NPL for the OTA TRP measurement is explained and the path loss at the receiver side is determined. Finally, TRP of a standard gain horn antenna at 38.5 GHz is measured by sampling the radiated transmit power of the antenna with 3D scan at various locations over a sphere.

8. TRP measurements in RC for 5G FR2 Base Stations

8.1 TRP measurements in RISE RC

8.1.1 Scope This chapter shows results and measurement uncertainty for a RC based method for the measurement of TRP from 5G BSs in the FR2 frequency range (39 GHz). The BS was emulated by a radio communication test station MT8000A, together with frequency converters to 39 GHz (MA80002A from Anritsu). All measurements were performed at the RISE EMC test facility in Borås, Sweden. The measurements were performed as a part of Activity A1.2.6 in the 21NRM03 MEWS project.

8.1.2 Introduction It can be shown that the TRP from an antenna, measured in a RC can be expressed as (described in [93]):

$$TRP = \frac{\langle P \rangle_N}{G_{ref} \eta_{rx}^{tot} G_{cable}} \quad (8-1)$$

where $\langle P \rangle_N$ is the received power, averaged over N mode-stirring states. The term η_{rx}^{tot} denotes the total radiation efficiency for the receiving antenna used in the measurement, and G_{cable} denotes the cable loss between the power measuring device and the antenna, often estimated from a S_{21} measurement of the cable with a VNA. G_{ref} is the chamber loss given by:

$$G_{ref} = \frac{\langle |S_{21}|^2 \rangle_M}{\eta_{tx}^{tot} \eta_{rx}^{tot}} \quad (8-2)$$

where $\langle |S_{21}|^2 \rangle$ is given by an average of S_{21} VNA measurements, over M different mode-stirring states, and η_{tx}^{tot} denotes the total radiation efficiency for the transmitting antenna used in the chamber loss measurement. When using the same antenna in the chamber loss measurement and in the TRP measurement, the TRP becomes:

$$TRP = \frac{\langle P \rangle_N \eta_{tx}^{tot}}{\langle |S_{21}|^2 \rangle_M G_{cable}} \quad (8-3)$$

When measuring the power of broadband communication signals, many methods can be used. In this report an integration over the channel bandwidth from measurements with smaller measuring Resolution Bandwidth (RBW) is used (integrated bandwidth method), similar to the channel power functionality implemented in many spectrum analysers. A similar approach is used for the estimation of the TRP of the broadband signal, which then becomes:

$$TRP_{est} = \frac{BW}{RBW n} \sum_{f \text{ in } BW} TRP_{RBW}(f) \quad (8-4)$$

$TRP_{RBW}(f)$ is the TRP at frequency f measured with a spectrum analyser with a specific RBW. BW is the channel bandwidth, RBW is the resolution bandwidth of the SA and n is the number of frequency points inside the channel bandwidth BW . For 5G FR2 signals a TDD signalling mode is used, so a TDD correction is multiplied to the integration above.

Figure 32: Chamber calibration factor measurement setup.

$$TRP_{est} = \frac{BW TDD_{corr}}{RBW n} \sum_{f \text{ in } BW} TRP_{RBW}(f) \quad (8-5)$$

Many of the equations above have a “dB counterpart”, and in the processing of measurement data presented below a mixture of the “linear versions” and the “dB versions” have been used.

Simplifications

It is expected that the antennas used in the measurements have very little power dissipated in its materials (purely metal antenna), therefore the radiation efficiency of the transmitting antenna used in the chamber loss measurement is estimated from the S_{11} measurement by:

$$\eta_{tx}^{tot} = (1 - |S_{11}^{tx}|^2) \quad (8-6)$$

where S_{11}^{tx} is measured at an antenna calibration site [94].

8.1.3 Measurements

8.1.3.1 Setups

The setups used in the measurements are shown with block diagrams in Figures 32 to 34 together with a list of the used measurement equipment in table 2.

8.1.3.2 Results

With the BS emulated by a Communication Tester, the tethered (cable-bound) power fed to the DL antennas in the RC can be measured and compared to the TRP measurement within the RC. Since standard gain horns are used as DL antennas it can be expected that the TRP will be close to the power fed to the DL antennas due to the high efficiency of standard gain horns. This ‘reference’ comparison is performed for each measurement case. For 2x2 MIMO, the reference is presented as the sum of the two tethered (cable-bound) powers. An extra measurement case is also included in the result comparison by adding a 3 dB attenuator to the DL antenna in SISO mode and to one of the DL antennas in 2x2 MIMO mode. The performance of the attenuator can be seen in Figure 35 together with a mean value over the largest

Figure 33: SISO measurement setup.

Figure 34: 2x2 MIMO measurement setup.

No.	Type	Name	Model
1	BSE	Anritsu Radio Communication Test Station	MT8000A
2	FR2 Ext1	Anritsu 39GHz RF converter	MA80002A
3	FR2 Ext2	Anritsu 39GHz RF converter	MA80002A
4	Antenna	Flann Std Gain antenna	22240-20
5	Antenna	Flann Std Gain antenna	22240-20
6	Antenna	EMCO Dual ridge horn antenna	3116
7	Cables	Measurement RF cables	-
8	SA	R&S Signal & Spectrum analyser	FSW43
9	Computer	Lenovo Laptop running measurement software	-
10	RC	Fourier reverberation chamber (3.7x2.6x4.5m)	-
11	VNA	R&S Vector Network Analyzer with calibration kit	ZNB40
12	Antenna	EMCO Dual ridge horn antenna	3116

Table 2: Measurement equipment.

Figure 35: Attenuator performance over signalling bandwidth.

signaling bandwidth used in these measurements. To be able to get full signaling from the BS without a DUT, the “call processing” in the BSE was turned off. Each TRP measurement is processed from 50 RC samples with the stirrers in a stepped motion mode. The chamber calibration factor was measured with 200 RC samples.

8.1.3.3 SISO Mode

Signalling bandwidth 50 MHz.

Figure 36: Comparison between reference measurement (left) and RC TRP measurement (right) with signalling bandwidth of 50 MHz. The difference between the measurements is 0.42 dB.

Figure 37: Comparison between antenna without 3 dB attenuator (left) and with 3 dB attenuator (right) with a signalling bandwidth of 50 MHz. Difference between measurements is 3.68 dB.

Signalling Bandwidth 100 MHz.

Figure 38: Comparison between reference measurement (left) and RC TRP measurement (right) with signalling bandwidth of 100MHz. The difference between the measurements is 0.42 dB.

Figure 39: Comparison between TRP for antenna without 3 dB attenuator (left) and with 3 dB attenuator (right) with signalling bandwidth of 100MHz. Difference between measurements is 3.61 dB.

Signalling Bandwidth 200 MHz.

Figure 40: Comparison between reference measurement (left) and RC TRP measurement (right) with signalling bandwidth of 200MHz. The difference between the measurements is 0.76 dB.

Figure 41: Comparison between TRP for antenna without 3 dB attenuator (left) and with 3 dB attenuator (right) for a signalling bandwidth of 200 MHz. Difference between measurements is 3.61 dB.

8.1.3.4 2x2 MIMO

Signalling Bandwidth 100 MHz

Figure 42: Comparison between reference measurements (left) and RC TRP measurement (right) with signalling bandwidth of 100MHz in 2x2 MIMO mode. The difference between the measurements is 0.41 dB.

Figure 43: Comparison between reference measurements (left) with attenuator on the second antenna and RC TRP measurement (right) with signalling bandwidth of 100MHz. The difference between the measurements is 0.07 dB.

Signalling Bandwidth 200 MHz

Figure 44: Comparison between reference measurements (left) and RC TRP measurement (right) with signalling bandwidth of 200MHz in 2x2 MIMO mode. The difference between the measurements is 0.55 dB.

Figure 45: Comparison between reference measurements (left) with attenuator on the second antenna and RC TRP measurement (right) with signalling bandwidth of 200MHz. The difference between the measurements is 0.38 dB.

Measurement of TRP for radio equipment, both BSs and user equipment (UE), is essential as the EU Radio Equipment Directive imposes it as an essential requirement [[98], [99]]. The purpose of these measurements is to ensure that any radio equipment should support the efficient use of the radio spectrum and conformity should be demonstrated by using OTA metrics such as TRP and equivalent isotropic radiated power (EIRP), as defined in the harmonized standards [[90], [100]]. Methodological details of the TRP measurements for millimetre-wave (mm-wave) MIMO BS systems and UE are outlined in 3GPP test specifications, namely, ETSI TS 138.141-2 [90] and ETSI TS 138.521-2 [91], respectively. However, conventional TRP measurement methods such as DFF, CATR, and near-field-to-far-field (NF-FF) techniques, share a major common drawback – long measurement time. TRP requires integration over the full radiation sphere so both DFF and CATR methods must mechanically scan azimuth/elevation with fine angular steps to avoid under-sampling, especially for narrow beams at mm-wave frequencies; when combined with multiple frequency bands, output power levels, and large sets of beam configurations, further increase complexity and the required number of measurement configurations explodes. High path loss at 5G NR FR2 frequencies further stretches the dwell times, as more averaging is needed to satisfy dynamic-range and repeatability targets. NF-FF method is even more time-consuming, requiring dense spatial sampling, dual polarization, phase stability, and extensive post-processing, such as probe correction and far-field reconstruction, especially for mm-wave MIMO equipment.

These challenges highlight the urgent need for a faster, accurate, and traceable TRP measurement approach that can significantly reduce test time while maintaining accuracy and traceability. Reverberation chamber (RC) is an over-moded reflecting environment providing statistically homogeneous and isotropic fields within its working volume [101]. Such capability makes RC a faster and often more cost-effective alternative to an anechoic chamber for the TRP testing. This subchapter presents a newly developed cost-effective and time-efficient method for measuring TRP for conformance testing of a 5G NR BS using the RC technique. A new testbed setup has been configured to rigorously evaluate the transmission characteristics between antennas inside the chamber, as well as the reflection power from the transmitting antenna within the RC. The measurement method has undergone calibration and verification to ensure reliability. The antenna efficiency, which can be used to calculate TRP, is obtained by using the proposed testbed. Its validity is confirmed by comparing results with those from a conventional VNA.

8.2.2 Testbed setup The testbed architecture is shown in Figure 46(a). There are two stages of test procedure, i.e., calibration and measurement stages. In the calibration stage (the relevant setup involved are shown in Figure 46(b), a Zadoff-Chu (ZC) orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) signal with intermediate frequency (IF) of 3.2 GHz and a bandwidth of 40 MHz is generated using a National Instruments (NI) PXIe-5451 waveform generator and in-phase and quadrature (IQ) modulator (NI PXIe-5611). This signal is up converted to RF at 26 GHz using a 22.8 GHz local oscillator (LO) signal from a Keysight N5173B EXG source.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 46: Illustrative diagram for: (a) the testbed architecture; (b) its calibration setup; (c) its measurement setup

The resulting mm-wave signal passes through a band-pass filter (AMWAV AWBPF25.5-26.5GC2), a power splitter (Mini-Circuits ZN2PD2-50-S+), RF switches (NI PXI-2599) and a four-port downconverter (Keysight M9362A-D01) into the four-channel vector transceiver (NI PXIe-5644R). At the receiver, fractional-delay and phase-difference estimation for

each channel are performed; the resulting corrections are applied in real time so that all channels remain phase-aligned over long runs. Digital signal processors can then perform channel estimation and analyses on the coherent data. The signal from one channel is utilized as the power/phase reference versus the other three channels. With the proposed scheme, reliable measurements can be carried out, and the measured data can be stabilized against the time-varying drift. As a result, this setup enables stable, coherent measurements and accurate frequency response estimation across all receiver channels. At the measurement stage (the relevant setup involved are shown in Figure 46c, the RF switches are switched to the measurement route (yellow color route as illustrated in Figure 46. A 5G NR waveform is transmitted from the Anritsu base-station emulator (BSE) MT8000A to a mm-wave extender MA80003A for up-conversion to FR2 signals at 26 GHz, then they pass through a coupler module, which is comprised of a 10-dB hybrid coupler and a power splitter (Mini-Circuits, ZN2PD-183W-S+).

Using this combination, one can reduce the interference by the signals reflected from the antenna to the reference signals, i.e., suppressing amplitude of S_{32} . The main path (through the S_{21} route) feeds the transmitting antenna Tx1 inside the RC, while two taps of the coupler module provide references; one from the coupler module with the route S_{31} (forward sample) for the phase and power normalization at each measurement and the other from the power divider at the route S_{42} (reverse sample) to monitor the mismatch power from the transmitting antenna. A coherent four-channel receiver ingests signals from route S_{31} , S_{42} , and from the two receiving antennas (Rx2, Rx3) inside the RC under a common LO signal distributed via a power splitter. The RF signals are then downconverted into IF signals, which are transmitted into the transceiver for digitization and signal processing. As a result, one can obtain time-aligned, self-referenced data required in deriving the transmission characteristics between antenna pairs or the S-parameters of SRx2-Tx1 and SRx3-Tx1. These data will be used to determine antenna efficiency and TRP of the transmitting antenna Tx1.

8.2.3 Design of the Software for Real-Time Processing The main challenge of the proposed method lies in measuring S-parameters using real 5G NR signals generated by the DUT, as required by 3GPP standards, rather than relying on traditional VNA techniques. To address this challenge, in this paper, a real-time, multi-channel software solution has been developed. It enables S-parameter measurements between multiple receiving channels by leveraging the 5G NR downlink waveform, ensuring compliance with standard requirements while maintaining measurement accuracy and efficiency. This software, incorporating the real-time processing capabilities of the multi-channel VST platform, can provide up to four channels with 80 MHz bandwidth per channel real-time measurement capability. Due to its inherited wide-band demodulation feature, it can hugely reduce the measurement duration compared with the sweeping-frequency-based VNA method. Figure 47 illustrates the real-time processing program structure, which consists of two consecutive steps, i.e., the calibration and measurement steps, respectively, same as the architecture shown in Figure 46. The calibration step, which is required to launch regularly during the measurement period, aims to measure and eliminate the channel response differences existing in the multiple RF receiving measurement channels. A ZC-OFDM waveform is generated by a dedicated RF generator in the calibration branch, see Figure 46. At the receiver side, a channel frequency response (CFR) estimation algorithm is applied to obtain the deviations in the relative CFRs of each RF channel, normalized to the reference channel, i.e. the receiving Channel 1 (denoted as Ch1). An iterative sampling adjustment is applied to eliminate the errors and uncertainties caused by sampling timing differences by a fractional delay resampling module with the estimated delay offsets as inputs. Since the measurement of relative CFRs is operation in the calibration RF branch, all differences between the measurement branch and calibration RF branch,

including cables, different ports in the RF switch, power dividers, adapters. etc., are carefully considered, measured in advance, and compensated in the CFR estimation processing. After measuring the relative CFRs, the whole system is switched to the measurement stage by simply switching the RF path to import the 5G NR downlink signal and executing the corresponding processing program, without interrupting the continuous signal streaming at the receivers. The measurement stage involves full data processing of the 5G NR downlink signal. It begins with time and frequency synchronization using the Synchronization Signal Block (SSB), followed by blind detection of the Physical Downlink Control Channel (PDCCH) to extract the Downlink Control Information (DCI) required for subsequent Physical Downlink Shared Channel (PDSCH) demodulation. As shown in Figure 46, the receive channel 1, Ch1, typically connected to the DUT's RF output through a coupler, serves as the reference channel due to its superior signal quality compared to the rest of the channels. In the next step, PDSCH demodulation processing is performed on the receiver Ch1, including channel estimation, equalization, and bit-level demodulation. The detected bit sequence is then used to reconstruct the transmitted downlink waveform through modulation, enabling accurate S-parameter measurements in the following stage. In the final step of the measurement stage, all receiving channels (Ch1, Ch2, Ch3, and Ch4) perform channel estimation using the reconstructed waveform as the reference waveform. To evaluate the OTA transmission characteristics, the influence of the RF measurement paths is removed by compensating with the previously stored relative CFR. This process, analogous to calibration in a VNA, effectively sets the calibration plane at the inputs of the VST receivers. As a result, accurate and traceable S-parameter measurements can be obtained.

Figure 47: Two-step VST-based S-parameters measurement program structure. The acronym definitions are: FFT – Fast Fourier-Transform; IFFT – Inverse FFT; CFR – Channel Frequency Response; PBCH – Physical Broadcast Channel; PDCCH – Physical Downlink Control Channel

8.2.4 Testbed verification To verify the testbed's performance for transmission measurements, we use a coupler module as a DUT by connecting the output port of the DUT to Ch2 and measure the transmission between Ports 1 and 2 or S_{21} . Figure 48 illustrates the configuration for the direct connection to the Ch2 cable. The insertion loss of all measurement cables was measured in advance using a VNA and then de-embedded with the postprocessing. The reference planes were set at the coupler input Port 1 and at the output Port 2 as shown in Figure 48. The transmission 21 of the coupler module was then measured using the proposed testbed and compared with the VNA results.

(a)

(b)

Figure 50: Amplitude and phase of measured S_{21} of the coupler module using the VNA and the proposed testbed when directly connected the output port of the coupler module to the receiver Ch3: (a) Amplitude; (b) Phase

(a)

(b)

Figure 51: Amplitude and phase of measured S_{21} of the coupler module using the VNA and the proposed testbed when directly connected the output port of the coupler module to the receiver Ch4: (a) Amplitude; (b) Phase

8.2.5 Measurement Results To determine antenna efficiency by the three-antenna method inside RC [102], we need to know the S-parameters of S_{21} , S_{31} and S_{32} . By using the proposed testbed, one can measure the transmission from antennas 1 to 2 and 1 to 3, which correspond to S_{21} and S_{31} while the S_{32} is separately obtained using the conventional VNA. Measurement setup inside the RC is shown in Figures 52. After obtaining all S_{21} , S_{31} , and S_{32} , total efficiency of the transmitting antenna is determined as:

$$\eta_{\text{tot}} = C_{\text{RC}} \frac{\langle |S_{21,s}|^2 \rangle \langle |S_{31,s}|^2 \rangle}{\omega \tau_{\text{RC}} \langle |S_{32,s}|^2 \rangle} \quad (8-7)$$

where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ means the average value of the S-parameter using any stirring method, ω is the angular frequency, T_{RC} is the chamber decay constant which can be extracted from the time-domain response of the chamber, $S_{ij,s}$ is the stirred part of the S-parameter or $S_{ij,s} = S_{ij} - \langle S_{ij} \rangle$, and C_{RC} is a constant defined as:

$$C_{\text{RC}} = \frac{16\pi^2 V}{\lambda^3} \quad (8-8)$$

Here, V is the volume of the RC and λ is the free-space wavelength. Figures 53(a) and (b) indicate the amplitude and phase of the transmission S_{21} , while Figures 54(a) and (b) show those of S_{31} , respectively. It is demonstrated that both results measured by the VNA and VST (the proposed testbed) resemble each other. The minor difference may be caused by different cable positions or bending when swapping the cables between the VNA setup and the testbed setup since the RC is a high-Q resonator where small differences in cable positions, antenna setup angle, or bending of the cable may affect total results. A high peak at the center frequency as indicated in Figure 53(a) and Figure 54(a) is caused by the DC component when the IF signals are converted into the baseband signal. This peak is cut off by using the average value between two neighboring values instead. Then, we performed the measurement of S_{21} and S_{31} on 400 step stirrer positions and calculated the antenna efficiency.

Figure 52: Experimental setup for antenna efficiency measurement using the RC: (a) illustrative diagram; (b) photo

Figure 53: Measured S_{21} between Antennas 2 and 1 placed inside the RC: (a) Amplitude; (b) Phase

Figure 54: Measured S_{31} between Antennas 3 and 1 placed inside the RC: (a) Amplitude; (b) Phase

Figure 55: Measurement results of antenna efficiency by the VNA and the proposed testbed using VST

Figure 55 shows the antenna efficiency of the transmitting antenna Tx1 measured by our testbed and the conventional VNA. Measurement results using the testbed are indicated in a red box around the center frequency at 25.875 GHz since the bandwidth of the receiver is limited to 40 MHz. Both results are in good agreement with the difference smaller than 5 %, demonstrating the validity of our testbed. A high peak at the center frequency is caused by DC component when the IF signals are converted into the baseband signal. The measured antenna efficiency is then used in derivation of the TRP which is defined as:

$$P_{\text{tot}} = \eta_{\text{tot}} P_{\text{in}} \quad (8-9)$$

where P_{in} is the input power to the antenna which can be measured by a spectrum analyzer. The total measurement time for 400-step stirrer positions is less than two hours when using the proposed testbed while it was nearly 14 hours when using the traditional VNA approach. Therefore, the measurement time is only 14 % or one seventh of the conventional method. After deriving the efficiency at each frequency inside the target band, the power of broadband communication signals can be derived as [93]:

$$TRP = \frac{BW}{N_f F_{ABW}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_f} P_{tot}^i \quad (8-10)$$

where P_{tot}^i is the TRP at i th frequency with a frequency-averaging bandwidth FABW (= 6 MHz), N_f is the number of frequency points inside the channel bandwidth BW, which is 40 MHz in our case. For average power of 0 dBm with 40 MHz bandwidth at the input port of the base station, the TRP can be evaluated as -0.33 dBm or 0.93 mW using the proposed testbed.

8.2.6 Conclusion This section presents a new cost-effective and time-efficient method for measuring TRP for conformance testing of a 5G NR BS inside a RC. The proposed testbed architecture provides accurate amplitude and phase of the S-parameters, which can be used in deriving the results for antenna efficiency and TRP. The measurement results show good agreement with the conventional approach using the VNA, while the measurement time reduces to only 14 % or one seventh of the conventional method. This demonstrated that the proposed method is time-efficient, and it is suitable for MIMO antenna systems.

9. Investigation of high-gain antenna effects during testing in RC at 77 GHz

9.1 Scope

This report presents the results of a measurement comparison between three antennas with different gain. The comparison was carried out in a RC, with the antennas operating in Tx mode. The purpose of the measurements was to investigate whether high-gain antennas can reveal potential issues related to the use of RCs for such antennas. These measurements were made as a part of the A1.2.6 activity in the 21NRM03 MEWS project.

9.2 Measurement setup

A block diagram of the measurement setup can be seen below, along with a list of the equipment used in Table 4. For each antenna, 500 measurements were captured with the spectrum analyser over 500 mode-stirring states, with the RF signal set to 77 GHz. The statistical behaviour of the samples was then compared to the theoretical behaviour of a well-stirred RC, and the results can be seen in the following sections. The gain of the different Tx antennas at 77 GHz are:

- 15 dBi for the A-Info horn antenna,
- 20 dBi for the Flann standard gain horn antenna, and
- 40 dBi for the Flann lens horn antenna.

A Flann standard gain horn was used as receive (Rx) antenna. The RC used in the test have dimensions: width x height x length equal to 3.7 x 2.6 x 4.5 m.

Figure 56: Block diagram of the measurement setup.

9.3 Evaluation of measurement data

9.3.1 Sample correlation

The auto correlation of the received power samples from each Tx antenna was compared to the rule of thumb $1/e$ correlation limit for a well-stirred RC [103]. As can be seen in Figure 57, all correlations are well below the $1/e$ correlation limit. The results can be interpreted as each antenna measurement has at least 500 independent samples.

No.	Type	Manufacturer	Model
1	Signal generator	Anritsu	Rubidium MG36241A
2	Frequency extender	VDI	WR12
3	Tx antenna: std gain horn	A-info	LB-12-15-A
4	Tx antenna: std gain horn	Flann	26240-20
5	Tx antenna: lens horn	Flann	26820-FA-1417
6	Rx antenna: std gain horn	Flann	27240-20
7	Frequency extender	R&S	FE110SR
9	Spectrum analyser	R&S	FSW85
10	RC	RISE	Fourier

Table 4: Measurement equipment.

Figure 57: Correlation of the received power samples for the different TX antennas.

9.3.2 Cumulative Distribution Function

The CDF of the captured power samples was compared with the theoretical CDF for RC measurements (Rayleigh distributed data) [104]. The samples gathered from the different antennas follow the theoretical CDF quite well.

Figure 58: CDF of the received power for the different TX antennas.

In addition to comparison between different antennas gains, the CDF was compared for different positions/polarisations of the lens antenna.

Figure 59: CDF of the received power for the different TX antennas.

9.3.3 Mean to Max ratio

Another metric to examine regarding RC stirring performance is the max to mean ratio, which is dependent on the number of independent samples in the measurements. From the section above it was concluded that each antenna measurement has at least 500 independent samples. In Figure 60 the mean to max ratio is plotted for the three different measurements together with the theoretical max to mean ratio for a measurement with 500 independent samples. The max to mean for the three antenna measurements all fall within the theoretical PDF.

Figure 60: CDF of the received power for the different TX antennas.

9.4 Conclusions

The evaluation of received power statistics from different gain Tx antennas suggests that RC measurements using high-gain antennas, up to at least 40 dBi, can be performed accurately in the given RC (3.7 x 2.6 x 4.5 m).

To decrease chamber loss, a smaller RC is preferable. However, a smaller RC increases the risk of line-of-sight coupling between Tx and Rx antennas, especially when using high gain Tx antennas. This could reintroduce the problem with high gain antennas in the RC and should be investigated further.

10. Inter-laboratory Comparisons

10.1 Scope

This chapter shows results for an anechoic-chamber-based and reverberation-chamber based method for the measurement of TRP from 5G Base Stations in the FR2 frequency range (39 GHz) provided in Chapter 7 and 8, respectively. These comparisons were performed as a part of Activity A1.2.5 in the 21NRM03 MEWS project.

10.2 Introduction

Due to increase in number of measurement conditions over multiple frequency bands, output power levels, and large sets of beam configurations, there is an increasing need in developing a new rapid measurement method for evaluating the performance of 5G NR FR2 devices. To compare these to current standardized approaches, two new mm-Wave mMIMO testbeds are developed for the measurement of the NR OTA RF parametric measurement of the total radiated power and the effective isotropic radiated power. One testbed is developed by NPL (United Kingdom) and the other by RISE (Sweden).

10.3 Measurement setups for total radiated power using reverberation chamber in RISE and NPL

One of the mm-Wave mMIMO testbeds has been developed using a base station emulator MT8000A, along with two frequency converters (MA80002A) from Anritsu Co. The measurements were performed at the RISE reverberation chamber which has a dimension of 3.7 m × 2.6 m × 4.5 m in Borås, Sweden. Measurement setup diagram is illustrated in Figure 61. It is composed of a radio communication test station (Anritsu, MT8000A), an RF converter (Anritsu, MA80002A), a standard gain horn antenna (Flann Microwave, Model no. 22240-20), a double ridge guided horn antenna (EMCO, Model no. 3116), and a spectrum analyzer (Rhode and Schwarz, FSW43).

Figure 61: Measurement setup for total radiated power in RISE, Sweden; BSE: base-station emulator, SA: spectrum analyzer

The other mm-Wave mMIMO testbed using a VST has been developed by NPL for total radiated power and effective isotropic radiated power measurements in an NR FR2 frequency band. The schematic diagram of the testbed is shown in Figure 46(a) and details of the architecture and software design are given in Sections 8.2.2 and 8.2.3, respectively. This system has been validated in both 26 GHz and 38 GHz bands. The measurements were performed inside the

NPL reverberation chamber with a dimension of 6.55 m × 5.85 m × 3.5 m. Measurement procedure of TRP is described in subchapter 7.7 and, hence, is omitted here.

10.4 Measurement results

10.4.1 RC (RISE) With the base-station emulator or a communication tester, the tethered (cable-bound) power fed to the downlink antenna in the RC can be measured and compared to the TRP measurement inside the RC. The standard gain horn antennas are used in experiments, and it is expected that the TRP will be close to the power fed into the antenna since high efficiency of the standard gain horn antenna. The measurements were carried out using the setup shown in Figure 61. Each TRP measurement is processed from 50 RC samples with the stirrers in a stepped motion mode while measurement of $\langle |S_{21}|^2 \rangle_M$ (see subchapter 8.2) and chamber loss was done with 200 RC samples. Figure 62, Figure 63, and Figure 64 show comparison between reference measured power and RC TRP measurements with a signal bandwidth of 50 MHz, 100 MHz, and 200 MHz, respectively. The reference power is measured by connecting the cable end before the transmitting antenna.

Figure 62: Comparison between (a) reference measurements and (b) RC TRP measurements with a signal bandwidth of 50 MHz. The difference between two measurements is 0.18 dB

Figure 63: Comparison between (a) reference measurements and (b) RC TRP measurements with a signal bandwidth of 100 MHz. The difference between two measurements is 0.42 dB

Figure 64: Comparison between (a) reference measurements and (b) RC TRP measurements with a signal bandwidth of 200 MHz. The difference between two measurements is 0.75 dB

It is shown that the measured TRPs are close to the reference power since the antenna efficiency is high for standard gain horn antenna. However, the reason that the differences between the reference power and TRP were larger for wider signal bandwidth is still unclear and needs further investigation. It might be attributed to the mode fluctuation nature of the reverberation chamber.

10.4.2 RC (NPL) using VST Before measuring the TRP using the NPL-developed testbed, the S-parameters between two standard gain horn antennas were measured and compared with those obtained using a VNA. Figure 65 shows the

measurement setup inside the RC. Three standard gain horn antennas (Flann Microwave, Model 22240-20) were used. The transmitting antenna is the same one employed in the experiments conducted at RISE, Sweden, for consistency and comparison. The center frequency of the 5G NR FR2 signal is 38.5 GHz with a bandwidth of 40 MHz. The designed testbed setup is used to measure the transmission from the Tx antenna to the Rx antenna. First, we compare the measured S_{21} results with those obtained using the conventional VNA method.

Figure 65: Measurement of TRP by using three-antenna method in NPL reverberation chamber

Figure 66 shows the ensemble S-parameter results obtained from the VNA and the testbed over 400 RC samples. It can be seen that both results agree reasonably well, with differences within approximately 3 dB, demonstrating the validity of the developed measurement system using VST.

Figure 66: Comparison between the ensemble S -parameter of S_{21} measured using VNA and that obtained from the developed testbed over 400 RC samples. Effective band indicates the band of the transmitted NR FR2 signal

Figure 67 shows the antenna efficiency of the Tx antenna measured by the testbed and the conventional VNA. Measurement results using the testbed are indicated in a red box around the center frequency at 38.5 GHz since the bandwidth of the receiver is only limited to 40 MHz. Both results are in good agreement with the difference smaller than 3 %, demonstrating again the validity of our testbed at the 38.5 GHz band. For average power of 0 dBm with 40 MHz bandwidth at the input port of the base station, the TRP of 5G NR FR2 signal is determined as -1.37 dBm or 0.73 mW using the testbed.

Figure 67: Total radiation efficiency of the standard gain horn antenna measured by using three-antenna method and the developed testbed

10.4.3 AC Direct Far-Field (DFF) Using VST (NPL) A testbed using the VST for direct far-field TRP measurement method inside the anechoic chamber has been developed. The architecture of the measurement setup is shown in Figure 27. Figure 68 shows the measurement inside the SMART chamber facility in NPL. The antenna tower at the transmitter side has a U-shaped arm for rotation in a roll direction. In order not to get the coaxial cable tangled with the tower and rotation arm, 2.92 mm-type joint rotation connector is used and attached to the end of the antenna tower. To make a rotation in azimuth direction, the antenna tower is set on the rotation stage with absorbers to reduce the reflection from the stage. A standard gain horn antenna (Flann Microwave, Model no.22240-20) is used as a transmit antenna and a broadband double ridge guided horn antenna (A-Info, Model no. LB-180400-15-C-KF) is used as a receiving antenna. The receiving antenna is fixed on antenna tower at 1.7 m far from the aperture of the transmitting antenna. Angle steps in both θ - and ϕ -directions are $\Delta\theta = \Delta\phi = 9^\circ$. Number of sampling points in θ - and ϕ -direction are then set to $N = 21$ and $M = 40$, respectively. This accounts for a total number of 840 measurements for each of two orthogonal components.

Figure 68: Measurement setup for AC direct far-field method in SMART chamber in NPL

Figures 69(a), (b), and (c) show the power measured at the VST for θ -polarization, φ -polarization, and combined polarization, respectively. The maximum receiving power of -61.92 dBm, corresponding to EIRP of -35.07 dBm at 38.5 GHz for combined polarization is obtained when $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\varphi = 297^\circ$. The TRP is evaluated as -54.27 dBm.

Figure 69: Measured power at the VST for (a) θ -polarization, (b) ϕ -polarization, and (c) combined polarization with number of measurement points of $N = 21$ and $M = 40$.

10.4.4 AC Mid-Field (NPL) Using VST The AC mid-field, or CFFNF (Combined Far-Field / Near-Field) method described in TR 38.884 is required because conventional direct far-field (FF) over-the-air (OTA) measurements for FR2 signals suffer from fundamental limitations caused by high path loss and cable loss. These limitations make certain RF test cases, particularly those involving high DL power and low UL power, either inaccurate or entirely untestable. In the FR2 bands (24–52 GHz), the free-space path loss is extremely high; for a typical far-field distance of 1 m, the loss exceeds 60–65 dB at 28–40 GHz. As a result, the radiated power becomes too weak to measure and often approaches the noise floor of the test system. Increasing the far-field distance only worsens the SNR problem, making TRP measurements unreliable or even infeasible. The key idea of using AC mid-field is to move the probe or the receiving antenna much closer to the DUT, e.g., 0.2–0.3 m. This can reduce path loss by 10–15 dB and dramatically improve SNR of the system. In TR 38.884, the signal received by the probe antenna from a transmitting antenna array is modelled as a superposition of the contributions of individual antenna elements:

$$\text{Signal}(\theta, \phi) = \sum_k a_k F_k(\theta_k, \phi_k) G_{\text{probe}}(\alpha_k, \beta_k) \frac{e^{-jkR_k}}{R_k} \quad (10-1)$$

where a_k is excitation coefficient of antenna element k , F_k is antenna element pattern, G_{probe} indicates probe antenna pattern, R_k denotes distance from element k to the probe, and $k=2\pi/\lambda$ is the wavenumber. For a fixed angular direction (θ, ϕ) , changing the measurement distance r (probe position) slightly changes all the element-to-probe distances $R_k(r)$, and therefore the measured power:

$$p(r) = |\text{Signal}|^2 \quad (10-2)$$

exhibits a specific distance dependence. The AC mid-field or CFFNF method approximates this distance dependence by using a power-series expansion in terms of $1/r$, and extracts the far-field EIRP/EIS as the constant (zeroth-order) term of this expansion. Received power can be expressed in terms of distance d as:

$$p(d) \approx C_0 + \frac{C_1}{d^2} + \frac{C_2}{d^4} \quad (10-3)$$

C_0 corresponds to the far-field EIRP/EIS (the term as $d \rightarrow \infty$) and the $1/d^4$ term is the dominant near-field residual after normalization. Figure 70 shows the measurement setup inside the anechoic chamber at NPL. The transmitting antenna is a standard gain horn antenna (Flann Microwave, Model 22240-20), and the receiving antenna is a double-ridge guide horn antenna (A-Info, Model LB-180400-15-C-KF). The gain of the receiving antenna must be known beforehand using (7-6). The testbed used for this measurement is the same as that used for the direct far-field method, shown in Figure 27. Measurement distances of 0.4, 0.5, and 0.6 m were selected, which lie within the radiating near-field. In this region, the far-field gain pattern of the receiving antenna is sufficiently accurate to be used as a correction term.

Table 5 summarizes the measured power, the power corrected using (7-6), and the power further corrected by compensating for the known $1/r^2$ free-space decay at 0.4, 0.5, and 0.6 m. By applying the distance-dependent fitting defined in (10-3), the far-field EIRP, corresponding to the fitting coefficient C_0 , is obtained as -32.21 dBm. Meanwhile, the EIRP measured directly at 0.9 m is -33.40 dBm, giving a difference of approximately 1.19 dB. This discrepancy may be attributed to the measurement distance at 0.9 m where the far-field condition is still insufficiently satisfied. It is also observed that while the measured power at 1.7 m was -63.66 dBm, the measured powers at 0.4, 0.5, and 0.6 m were -47.36 , -49.01 , and -50.27 dBm, respectively, more than 10 dB higher than that measured at 1.7 m, thereby significantly improving the SNR of the measurement. These results demonstrate that, using the proposed testbed, the EIRP can be accurately estimated at reduced distances, leading to improved SNR and enhanced measurement reliability, particularly when dealing with NR FR2 signals in the millimeter-wave frequency band.

Figure 70: Measurement setup for CNFF method inside the SMART chamber in NPL

Table 5: Measurement results for measured power, corrected power, and corrected power compensated with its distance.

Distance (m)	Measured power (dBm)	Corrected power P_{corr} (dBm)	$P_{corr} \times d^2$ (dBm)
0.4	-47.36	-33.03	-40.99
0.5	-49.01	-32.74	-38.76
0.6	-50.27	-32.42	-36.85

10.5 Conclusion

This section presents a new cost-effective and time-efficient method for measuring the TRP of 5G NR BS using a RC. A testbed employing real 5G NR signals is designed to accurately characterize transmission between transmitting and receiving antennas inside the RC. Its validity is confirmed by comparing results with those from a conventional VNA. The testbed is then used to evaluate antenna efficiency via three-antenna method. Finally, TRP is derived for conformance testing, and the time-efficiency of the proposed method is demonstrated by comparing the total measurement time with the VNA-based approach.

11. Conclusion

This report has presented work focused on the development of cost-effective and time-efficient metrological methods for measuring the performance characteristics of new radio RF parametrics. Several physical layer metrics, such as TRP, effective isotropic radiated power, and effective isotropic radiated power. To balance between the measurement efficiency and the measurement accuracy, the standard RF metric conformance testing approaches and the proposed measurement methodologies (using signal processing enabled algorithms/methods) are rigorously studied.

The effects of current practical testing setups, which are typically compact and non-anechoic due to cost and measurement time considerations that limit measurement accuracy has been studied. The work carried out has addressed such challenge by:

1. Development of algorithms which can retrieve new radio conformance testing results in ideal conditions based on measured data in non-ideal scenarios.

- 2 Development of testbeds to validate the developed algorithms and assess the relevant measurement uncertainties.

3. Development of cost-effective alternatives based on mid-field and RC+CE methods, and where applicable, will build a simulation framework and measurement setup to provide a platform for traceability for new radio conformance testing and future algorithm development.

4. Conducted a round-robin measurement campaign to quantify the associated uncertainties introduced by the different measurement methods.

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